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Bird damage assessment in broad beans (*Vicia faba*) and strawberry (*Fragaria ananassa*) at Qalyubia Governorate, Egypt

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Abstract

Bird damage is a serious problem for the agricultural sector in Egypt, it causes great economic losses by attacking various crops and fruit. Thus, there is an urgent need for accurate damage assessment, which supports any research efforts to reduce that damage. The goals of this study were to measure the use of traditional bird deterrent practices (Scarecrows and reflecting colored plastic stripe) and not use any deterrent practices, on bird damage in broad beans and strawberry fields during the ripening and fruiting stages. The percentage of bird damage in broad bean fields using visual bird deterrent practices and without any deterrent practices (Control) reached 20.51 and 19.31 %, respectively. While in strawberry fields it was $3.14 \pm 0.47\%$ in fields using visual bird deterrent practices and $3.74 \pm 0.60\%$ in fields without any deterrent practices (Control). Our findings cleared that birds were quickly accustomed to the deterrent practices and used the deterrent equipment as perching sites to attack the crops. It's obvious that these methods didn't affect the harm caused by birds.

Introduction

Birds have different roles in the agricultural ecosystem (Garcia *et al.*, 2020). First, a positive role as natural enemies of large numbers of invertebrates and these are a beneficial impact on farmers, but there's a negative role too, as a threat to several agricultural crops (Issa *et al.*, 2019 and Garcia *et al.*, 2020).

It predated vegetable, fruit crops and spoils grain, causing damage to several crops during different growth stages (Pejchar *et al.*, 2018), e.g., Broad beans, corn, sorghum, maize, cucumber, peas, groundnut, sunflower, grapes, guava and strawberry are among those crops (Khattab *et al.*, 2002; Attia, 2006; Abbasy *et al.*, 2012;

Kale *et al.*, 2014 and Issa and El-Bakhshawngi, 2018). This leads to economical loss for farmers up to several millions of dollars worth of agricultural crops (Dolbeer *et al.*, 1994).

Broad beans (*Vicia faba* L.) are one of the most strategic legume crops in Egypt, due to their importance as a major part of the Egyptian local dishes (Hegab *et al.*, 2014). Egypt is one of the eight main producers of broad beans (150,000 tons that are equivalent to 3.46% of the global production), however, this amount isn't sufficient for consumed and Egypt being imported from abroad (Rawal and Navarro, 2019).

Thus, increasing broad bean production is a main target in the Egyptian agricultural strategy in order to face the demand of the growing population. However, one of the hitches facing this crop is its yield instability which is related to several factors including pests (Darwish and Abdalla, 1997). Birds are one of the main pests for broad beans, they attack pods during the fruiting stage and depredate seeds resulting in losses of approximately 18.65% (Attia, 2006) and reached to 20.40% (Abdel-Gawad *et al.*, 2010).

Strawberry (*Fragaria ananassa* Duchesne) is an important crop in Egypt. Its production increased in recent years and accordingly, Egypt ranked as the fourth largest producer in the world (Essa, 2015). Therefore, strawberry is considered one of the crops that contribute to the national income through exporting (Abd-Elgawad, 2019).

But strawberry fruits have a unique characterization (Deep red color, juicy taste, smooth texture with an aroma) makes them desirable and vulnerable to attack by birds leading to

a yield loss of 6.42% (Khattab *et al.*, 2002), and may be reached up to 30% (Sharma *et al.*, 2019).

Through that paper we highlight the problem of bird damage in broad beans during the ripening stage and strawberries during the fruiting stage with a comparison between using traditional bird deterrent practices (Scarecrows and reflecting colored plastic stripes) and not using any deterrent practices, in an attempt to reduce bird damage on these strategic crops at Qalyubia Governorate, Egypt.

Materials and methods

1. Study sites:

The study was conducted in Qaha and Shibin El Qanater districts, Qalyubia Governorate, Egypt (Figure 1), from September 2020 to May 2021. The study area has histories of grower complaints due to severe bird injuries. Dominant bird species found were house sparrow, *Passer domesticus niloticus* Nicoll and Bonhote (Passeriformes: Passeridae) and hooded crow, *Corvus corone* L. (Passeriformes: Corvidae).

Figure (1): Study sites at Qaha and Shibin El Qanater districts, Qalyubia Governorate, Egypt where fields cultivated with broad beans and strawberry were located.

2. Broad beans fields:

Fields cultivated with broad beans were chosen at Qaha district (30°29087'N, 31°21657'E) and (30°29585'N, 31°20910'E). The selected fields (10 feddans), were divided into two equal divisions to assess bird damage. In the first division we used visual deterrent practices (Traditional scarecrows and reflecting colored plastic stripes) in an attempt to reduce bird damage. The second division was used as a control. Three replicates in both divisions were chosen (1/2 feddan/ each), and were separated by more than 500 m² (Issa *et al.*, 2019). Ten fixed samples were chosen in each

$$\text{Damage \%} = (0.0 \times S1 + 0.25 \times S2 + 0.50 \times S3 + 0.75 \times S4 + 1.0 \times S5) / N \times 100$$

Where :

S¹= Number of undamaged pods, S²= Number of pods with 25% damaged, S³= Number of pods with 50% damaged, S⁴= Number of pods with 75% damaged, S⁵= Number of pods with 100% damaged and N= Total number of investigated pods.

3. Strawberry fields:

Two farms cultivated with strawberries were chosen at El Zahweyeen village (30°25595'N, 31°27703'E) and (30°26346'N, 31°26540'E), Shibin El Qanater districts, to determine bird damage to strawberry fruit. Two replicates (4 feddans) in each farm were selected and twenty samples were chosen randomly for investigation. Each sample consists of ten successive plants (Gonthier *et al.*, 2019). The number of damaged and undamaged fruits was counted in each plant. The percentage of damage was calculated according to Khattab *et al.* (2002) by the following formula :

$$\% \text{Damage} = \frac{\text{No. Of damaged fruits}}{\text{Total No. of examined fruits}} \times 100$$

4. Data analysis:

Statistical analysis of data was done using CoStat (2005) statistical software. Mean \pm standard error (SE) of bird damage was calculated and

replicate and inspected weekly for 6 weeks. Ten successive plants in each sample were inspected to estimate the degree of bird damage to pods during the ripening stage (After pods emergence and during seed-filling), the damage was calculated for the first week, then the second week by calculating and subtracted from the previous week and so on till the latest week. The degrees of damage were classified into four categories (0, 25, 50, 75 and 100%) depending on the number of seeds existing in the pods. The total percentage of damage was calculated according to Elrawy *et al.* (2021) using the following formula:

differences between weeks were analysis at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance by Duncan (1955).

Results and discussion

1. Broad beans study:

The main bird pest attacking broad beans in our study was the house sparrow. Birds start to attack broad bean pods at the milky stage. It feeds on pods after emergencies and during the seed-filling stage. As a result, hollowed or pecked and eaten seeds within pods were found.

Fields with and without visual bird deterrent practices were inspected weekly, for 6 successive weeks, to determine the percentage of damage. Data illustrated in Table (1) and Photo (1) revealed that, the percentage of damage increased in fields without any bird deterrent practices (Control) during the grain-filling period till the third week, then decreased dramatically during hardness till harvest. In fields with visual bird deterrent practices (Scarecrows and colored plastic stripe) bird damage was 5.01%. Once the deterrent practices were employed the percentage of damage decreased to 3.47%, but quickly birds realized that there was no threat to them, thus attacking broad beans again and using

the deterrent equipment as perching sites, followed that, an increase in damage to reach 6.16%.

Statistical analysis was carried out to compare the damage between weeks and between fields with visual bird deterrent practices and control fields. The comparison showed a highly significant difference at 5% level of **Table (1): The percentage of damage at fields with and without visual bird deterrent practices in broad beans.**

significance ($P \leq 0.05$) between different weeks. In contrast, there is no significant difference between fields with bird deterrent practices and the control fields during different weeks. There were no significant effects for using visual bird deterrent practices to prevent bird damage in broad beans, $t = 0.15$, $p = 0.44$.

Week	With visual bird deterrent practices	Without visual bird deterrent practices (Control)	Mean \pm S.E.	LSD $_{0.05}$
1 st	5.01 ^{ab}	4.94 ^b	4.96 \pm 0.07	1.37
2 nd	3.47 ^{bc}	5.52 ^{ab}	4.83 \pm 0.68	1.93 ^{**}
3 rd	6.16 ^a	6.18 ^a	6.17 \pm 0.18	1.91
4 th	2.57 ^{cd}	2.43 ^c	2.81 \pm 0.26	3.58
5 th	1.54 ^{cd}	1.05 ^d	1.21 \pm 0.24	1.44
6 th	0.56 ^d	0.39 ^d	0.45 \pm 0.08	1.24
Total	19.31	20.51	20.43	
Mean \pm S.E.	3.22 \pm 0.86	3.42 \pm 1.0007		2.94
LSD $_{0.05}$	2.02 ^{**}	1.63 ^{***}		
t-value	0.15141			
p-value	0.44133			

Values in column followed by different letters are significantly at $P \leq 0.05$ according to Duncan's multiple range tests.

Photo (1): Damage caused by birds in broad bean pods.

2. Strawberry study:

Strawberry damage occurred during the fruiting stage (Photo 2). Hooded crow and house sparrow are the primary bird pests to strawberry fruits in our study sites. Birds peck strawberry fruits causing wounds to flesh and scrape them .

Strawberry fields were selected to compare applying visual bird

deterrent practices (Scarecrows and colored plastic stripes) to deter birds from damaging strawberry fruits with other fields that not using any practices (Control). Fields were inspected for bird damage during the fruiting period for 13 weeks .

The average bird damage in control fields was $3.74 \pm 0.60\%$ of fruits and it was almost the same with fields

using visual bird deterrent practices $3.14 \pm 0.47\%$. The highest percentage of damage was recorded during the first week in both control fields and fields with visual bird deterrent practices (7.86 and 5.37%), while the lowest was in the last week with (0.45 and 0.22%), respectively (Table 2).

Statistical analysis indicated a highly significant difference between weeks at ($P \leq 0.05$) in all fields, but there was no significant difference between control fields and fields using visual deterrent practices in the same inspected week, except during the first week which represented highly significant difference.

Table (2): The percentage of damage fruits at fields with and without visual bird deterrent practices in strawberry.

Week	With visual bird deterrent practices	Without visual bird deterrent practices (Control)	Mean \pm S.E.	LSD $_{0.05}$
1 st	5.37 ^a	7.86 ^a	6.61 \pm 1.24	1.15***
2 nd	5.25 ^{ab}	6.25 ^b	5.75 \pm 0.5	1.28
3 rd	4.54 ^{abc}	5.90 ^c	5.22 \pm 0.68	1.95
4 th	4.22 ^{bcd}	4.52 ^{cd}	4.37 \pm 0.15	2.12
5 th	4.18 ^{bcde}	4.49 ^{cd}	4.33 \pm 0.15	0.66
6 th	3.93 ^{cde}	4.32 ^{cd}	4.12 \pm 0.19	0.99
7 th	3.40 ^{def}	3.89 ^d	3.64 \pm 0.24	1.03
8 th	3.10 ^{efg}	3.70 ^d	3.40 \pm 0.3	0.65
9 th	2.43 ^{fg}	2.54 ^e	2.48 \pm 0.05	0.68
10 th	2.29 ^g	2.50 ^e	2.39 \pm 0.10	0.55
11 th	1.17 ^h	1.23 ^f	1.2 \pm 0.03	0.80
12 th	0.68 ^h	1.005 ^f	0.84 \pm 0.16	0.92
13 th	0.22 ^h	0.45 ^f	0.33 \pm 0.11	0.77
Total	40.78	48.65	20.43	
Mean \pm S.E.	3.14 \pm 0.47	3.74 \pm 0.60		0.44*
LSD $_{0.05}$	1.08***	1.14***		
t-value	0.726			
p-value	0.237			

Values in column followed by different letters are significantly at $P \leq 0.05$ according to Duncan's multiple range tests.

Photo (2): Damage caused by birds in strawberry fruits.

In our study, it was found that the total cumulative of bird damage in broad beans during the whole mature stage, reached 20.51% in fields that used visual bird deterrent practices and 19.31 % in fields without any deterrent practices (Control), similar results were found by Abdel-Gawad *et al.* (2010) in Assiut Governorate, Egypt. They found that broad beans average damage was 18.23%, and the house sparrow was the main bird that attacked broad bean pods as soon as they appeared. Attia (2006) reported that the bird damage was higher during the first stages of maturity after pods emergence (18.65%), but soon it decreased rapidly till stopped when seeds become hard .

We also found that there was no significant difference between using visual bird deterrent practices and without using it (Control). In line with this result, Gilsdorf *et al.* (2002) found that traditional visual bird deterrent does not provide sufficient protection .

We also noticed that the birds used the visual deterrent devices as perches to attack broad bean plants from different directions; it was explained by Wang *et al.* (2020) that birds had accustomed to the visual devices in less than 7 days .

When we assessed bird damage in strawberries, we found that average bird damage in control fields was 3.74%, this level of damage was found in other studies. In Egypt, Khattab *et al.* (2002) estimated that bird damage was about 5.57% in strawberry fields. In California USA, Gebhardt *et al.* (2011) estimated that rodent and bird damage to strawberry fruit reached 2.6%. In the same trend, a recent study in California, USA by Gonthier *et al.* (2019) revealed that bird damaged 3.2% of the fruits .

Our study cleared that bird damage in strawberry fruits was higher at the onset of the fruiting stage, this may be because there was no other food

round during the first period and afterward the other crops (Such as broad beans, peas, wheat, etc.) are available during that time of the year (From January to May). Also, bird feed on insects found in strawberry fields and thus it's tended to be insect and leaves the crop (Gonthier *et al.*, 2019).

Birds are important pests under Egyptian agro-ecosystems. It attacks different economic important crops such as broad beans and strawberries, causing a big amount of damage. The mean percentage of bird damage in strawberry fruit during the study period was 3.74 and 3.14%, while in broad beans it was 3.42 and 3.22% in fields free from any deterrent practices (Control) and fields using visual deterrent practices respectively.

The study demonstrated that using visual deterrent practices such as traditional scarecrows and plastic stripes to minimize bird damage in broad bean pods and strawberry fruits doesn't differ significantly from those without using any visual deterrent practices. Thus, these findings can greatly provide early insight for further research and damage control programs. Also, further studies about bird deterrent practices are needed to determine how birds actually respond and become habituated to visual deterrent practices. In addition, there's an urgent need to study the relationship between growing alternative food as bird temptation and bird deterrent practices.

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A faunistic survey of Pteromalidae (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea) in Golestan Province, Northern Iran, with an updated checklist of Iran

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Iran.

Abstract

During a faunistic survey in Golestan province (Northern Iran), 12 species of Pteromalidae (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea) in 11 genera were collected and identified. Two species, *Dipara claviger* (Kieffer, 1906) and *Halticoptera triannulata* (Erdos, 1946) are newly recorded from Iran. Updated checklist of Iranian Pteromalidae comprises 295 species in 124 genera is given.

Introduction

Pteromalidae are the third most speciose family of Chalcidoidea after Eulophidae and Encyrtidae, with 4,257 extant and 26 fossil species in 648 genera (Ghahari *et al.*, 2021). They are distributed in all biogeographical areas of the world, and are mostly primary or secondary, solitary or gregarious parasitoids of holometabolous insects, most commonly of Lepidoptera, Coleoptera and Diptera (Goulet and Huber, 1993; Bouček and Heydon, 1997 and Gibson *et al.*, 2021).

The most comprehensive catalogue of Iranian Pteromalidae has been published by Gibson *et al.* (2021) with 276 valid species and subspecies belonging to 120 genera and 16 subfamilies. References to all the Iranian records with their distribution within Iran and their Iranian hosts are available in it, together with global

distribution and taxonomic remarks. Additionally, eight species and four genera were excluded from the fauna of Iran by the mentioned catalogue. After that, other authors have made contributions to the Iranian fauna as follow:

Ghahari (2020): *Dinotiscus aponius* (Walker, 1848), and *Homoporus laeviusculus* Erdős, 1953,
Lotfalizadeh *et al.* (2020): *Homoporus febriculosus* (Girault, 1917), *Norbanus persicus* Lotfalizadeh and Rasplus, 2020, and *Stenomalina delvarei* Lotfalizadeh and Rasplus, 2020,
Rahmani *et al.* (2020): *Harrizia mira* Delucchi, 1962, Shojaey *et al.* (2020): *Rhynchocoelia impar* (Walker, 1836),
Rahmani *et al.* (2021): *Dinarmus altifrons* (Walker, 1862), and *Syntomopus incurvus* Walker, 1833,
Shojaey *et al.* (2021): *Coelopisthia areolata* Askew, 1980, *Norbanus*

brevicornis Szelenyi, 1974, *Pachyneuron gibbiscuta* Thomson, 1878, and *Sphegigaster pedunculiventris* (Spinola, 1808), Rahmani *et al.* (2022): *Blascoa ephedrae* Askew, 1997, *Plutothrix trifasciata* (Thomson, 1878), and *Homoporus pulchripes* Erdős, 1953 and Taher *et al.* (2022): *Mesopolobus aspilus* (Walker, 1835).

Of course, in addition to the mentioned papers, some other faunistic works have been published on Iranian Pteromalidae but without new country records; so, we do not consider them in this checklist.

Since the catalogue of Gibson *et al.* (2021) comprises all the published records until the end of 2019, so we represent an updated checklist includes all the data after the mentioned catalogue together with two new records (Totally with 19 species further than it).

Materials and methods

The pteromalid specimens of this faunistic survey were caught using Malaise traps and sweeping net in some regions of Golestan province (Northern Iran) during June to July 2015 and August to September 2017. The specimens are preserved in the private collection of the second author. Here we follow Noyes (2022) for nomenclature, classification and distributional data.

Results and discussion

List of species

In this faunistic survey, in total, 12 species of Pteromalidae within 11 genera were collected and identified from Golestan province.

1. Genus *Caenacis* Förster, 1856

1.1. *Caenacis lauta* (Walker, 1835)

Material examined: 2♀♀, Golestan province, Galikesh, Dar-Abad, 11.6.2015.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, England,

France, Germany, Hungary, Iran, Italy, Moldova, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden and Ukraine.

2. Genus *Chlorocythus* Graham, 1956

2.1. *Chlorocythus breviscapus* Graham, 1965

Material examined: 1♀, Golestan province, Bandargaz, Karkandeh, 27.7.2015.

General distribution: Czech Republic, England, Germany, Hungary, Netherlands, Sweden, Turkey (Noyes, 2022) and Iran (Gibson *et al.*, 2021).

3. Genus *Dibrachys* Förster, 1856

3.1. *Dibrachys microgastri* (Bouché, 1834)

Material examined: 1♂, 3♀♀, Golestan province, Kordkoy, Salikandeh, 10.9.2017; 2♂♂, Golestan province, Golestan National Park, 24.9.2017.

General distribution: Afghanistan, Algeria, Argentina, Australia, Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bosnia Hercegovina, Brazil, Bulgaria, Canada, Chile, China, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Egypt, Eritrea, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, India, Iran, Italy, Japan, Kazakhstan, Kirgizia, Korea, Mexico, Moldova, Morocco, Netherlands, New Zealand, North Africa, Pakistan, Peru, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, South Africa, Spain, Sudan, Sweden, Switzerland, Syria, Tajikistan, Tunisia, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, England, USA, Uruguay, former USSR, Uzbekistan and former Yugoslavia.

4. Genus *Dipara* Walker, 1833

4.1. *Dipara claviger* (Kieffer, 1906)

Material examined: 2♀♀, Golestan province, Golestan National Park, 24.9.2017. New record for Iran.

General distribution: Bosnia Hercegovina, Croatia, Greece, Italy, Romania, Turkey (Noyes, 2022) and Iran (This study).

5. Genus *Halticoptera* Spinola, 1811

5.1. *Halticoptera patellana* (Dalman, 1818)

Material examined: 1♂, 1♀, Golestan province, Minoodasht, Qaleh-Ghafeh, 22.9.2017.

General distribution: Belgium, Brazil, Canada, Canary Islands, Chile, China, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Hawaii, Italy, Japan, Mexico, Montenegro, Netherlands, Peru, Romania, Russia, Sweden, Switzerland, Taiwan, Trinidad and Tobago, Turkey, United Kingdom, USA (Noyes, 2022) and Iran (Gibson *et al.*, 2021).

5.2. *Halticoptera triannulata* (Erdos, 1946)

Material examined: 2♀♀, Golestan province, Golestan National Park, 24.9.2017. New record for Iran.

General distribution: Austria, China, Czech Republic, Germany, Hungary, Kazakhstan, Moldova, Romania, Slovakia, Sweden, Turkey, United Kingdom (Noyes, 2022) and Iran (This study).

6. Genus *Mesopolobus* Westwood, 1833

6.1. *Mesopolobus sericeus* (Förster, 1770)

Material examined: 3♀♀, Golestan province, Galikesh, Dar-Abad, 11.6.2015.

General distribution: Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Denmark, England, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iran, Israel, Italy, Kazakhstan, Moldova, Netherlands, Romania, Spain, Sweden, Turkey, Ukraine and Wales.

7. Genus *Nasonia* Ashmead, 1904

7.1. *Nasonia vitripennis* (Walker, 1836)

Material examined: 1♂, 3♀♀, Golestan province, Galikesh, Dar-Abad, 11.6.2015; 3♂♂, 2♀♀, Golestan province, Gorgan, Naharkhoran, 23.8.2017.

General distribution: Argentina, Australia, Austria, Belgium, Brazil, Canada, Chile, China, Croatia, Czech

Republic, Denmark, Egypt, England, France, Germany, Hawaii, India, Israel, Italy, Japan, Kazakhstan, Kirgizia, Korea, Madeira, Moldova, Netherlands, New Caledonia, New Zealand, North Africa, Norway, Poland, Romania, Senegal, Serbia, Slovakia, South Africa, South Korea, Spain, Sri Lanka, Sweden, Tajikistan, Turkey, USA, Uzbekistan, Zimbabwe (Noyes, 2022) and Iran (Gibson *et al.*, 2021).

8. Genus *Pachyneuron* Walker, 1833

8.1. *Pachyneuron aphidis* (Bouché, 1834)

Material examined: 1♀, Golestan province, Gorgan, Ziarat, 25.8.2017; 3♂♂, Golestan province, Kordkoy, Salikandeh, 10.9.2017; 1♂, 2♀♀, Golestan province, Minoodasht, Qaleh-Ghafeh, 22.9.2017.

General distribution: Argentina, Armenia, Australia, Belgium, Brazil, Bulgaria, Canada, Canary Islands, Caucasus, Chile, China, Colombia, Croatia, Cuba, Czech Republic, Egypt, El Salvador, France, Germany, Greece, Hawaii, Hungary, India, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Italy, Japan, Kazakhstan, Kirgizia, Korea, Libya, Macedonia, Mexico, Moldova, Montenegro, Morocco, Netherlands, New Zealand, Pakistan, Peru, Poland, Puerto Rico, Romania, Russia, Rwanda, Serbia, Slovakia, South Korea, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Syria, Tajikistan, Taiwan, Trinidad & Tobago, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, United Kingdom, USA, Uruguay, USSR, Venezuela, Yemen and former Yugoslavia.

9. Genus *Pteromalus* Swederus, 1795

9.1. *Pteromalus puparum* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined: 1♀, Golestan province, Bandargaz, Karkandeh, 27.7.2015; 2♂♂, 3♀♀, Golestan province, Gorgan, Naharkhoran, 23.8.2017.

General distribution: Algeria, Australia, Austria, Azores, Barbados,

Belgium, Bermuda, Bolivia, Bulgaria, Canada, Canary Islands, Chile, China, Croatia, Czech Republic, Egypt, El Salvador, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hawaii, Hungary, India, Iran, Iraq, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Japan, Kazakhstan, Kirgizia, Macedonia, Madeira, Malaysia, Moldova, Mongolia, Nepal, Netherlands, New Zealand, North Africa, Pakistan, Papua New Guinea, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Saint Lucia, Saudi Arabia, Serbia, Slovakia, South Africa, South Korea, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Tajikistan, Taiwan, Turkey, Ukraine, United Kingdom, USA, Uruguay, former USSR, Uzbekistan and former Yugoslavia.

10. Genus *Systasis* Walker, 1834

10.1. *Systasis tenuicornis* Walker, 1834

Material examined: 1♂, 1♀, Golestan province, Bandargaz, Karkandeh, 27.7.2015.

General distribution: Belgium, China, England, Germany, Hungary, Iran, Kazakhstan, Romania, Spain and Sweden.

11. Genus *Trychnosoma* Graham, 1957

11.1. *Trychnosoma punctipleura* (Thomson, 1878)

Material examined: 1♀, Golestan province, Gorgan, Ziarat, 25.8.2017.

General distribution: Czech Republic, France, Iran, Netherlands, Slovakia, Sweden and England.

Undetermined species

In addition to the mentioned 12 identified species, the below specimens were collected.

1. *Cea* sp.

Material examined: 1♀, Golestan province, Kordkoy, Salikandeh, 10.9.2017.

2. *Glyphognathus* sp.

Material examined: 1♀, Golestan province, Minoodasht, Qaleh-Ghafeh, 22.9.2017.

3. *Hemitrichus* sp.

Material examined: 1♂, Golestan province, Bandargaz, Karkandeh, 27.7.2015.

4. *Pteromalus* sp.

Material examined: 2♂♂, 3♀♀, Golestan province, Golestan National Park, 24.9.2017.

5. *Sphexigaster* sp.

Material examined: 2♂♂, Golestan province, Gorgan, Ziarat, 25.8.2017; 1♂, Golestan province, Minoodasht, Qaleh-Ghafeh, 22.9.2017.

6. *Toxeuma* sp.

Material examined: 1♂, 2♀♀, Golestan province, Gorgan, Naharkhoran, 23.8.2017.

The results of several faunistic surveys on Iranian Pteromalidae indicate that the fauna of these parasitoids is diverse in this country. Until now, species diversity of pteromalids in Northern parts of Iran has poorly been studied. Due to the high diversity of vegetation in Northern Iran, and consequently abundance of pteromalids' host species (Larvae and pupa of Lepidoptera, Coleoptera and Diptera), there is a very rich fauna of these parasitoid wasps in this area (Southern parts of the Caspian Sea). More intensive and extensive surveys by Malaise traps and rearing of the hosts of these parasitoids may yield not only more species of Pteromalidae, but also determination of parasitoid-host relationships in order to establishment of biological control programs.

Recently Rahmani *et al.* (2022) excluded a considerable number of pteromalid species from the catalogue of Gibson *et al.* (2021), and stated that all the pteromalid species recorded by Abd-Rabou *et al.* (2005a and 2019) and Sakenin *et al.* (2008a, b, and 2019) are irrelevant records to Iran. None of the authors of the mentioned paper (Rahmani *et al.* 2022) requested to re-examine the voucher specimens which all of them were identified or confirmed by the authorized chalcidologists; of

course, neither of the authors of the mentioned paper is authorized expert on Pteromalidae because of several published works on various families of Hymenoptera, and even other insect orders.

Certainly, considering the records under doubtful based on prediction, prejudice or unjustified reasons can't be trusted. In order to exclusion a taxon from a fauna, concrete and reliable taxonomic evidences are necessary, not citing to an old paper (Abd-Rabou *et al.*, 2005b) included a few misidentified species of another taxon (Vespidae!)¹. On the other hand, all the vespine misidentified species of Abd-Rabou *et al.* (2005b) were discussed and excluded by Dvorak, Ghahari, Carpenter and Abbasi (2012), as well as the masarine misidentified species in another paper. Therefore, there is no need for hasty criticism against authors who always corrected misidentified taxa through re-examining of specimens by the authorized experts.

Misidentification is common in taxonomic works, and respecting H. Lotfalizadeh's taxonomic papers, other three authors of the mentioned paper (Rahmani *et al.*, 2022) had scientific mistakes (Especially doubtful records) in their works. It is important for a researcher to have the courage and honesty to correct the prior published scientific mistakes. Additionally, the authors of the mentioned paper claimed wrongly that the papers Abd-Rabou *et al.* (2005a, 2019) and Sakenin *et al.* (2008a, b, 2019) were published without a peer-review process; while all the mentioned journals are peer-reviewed and the papers were reviewed by at least two anonymous reviewers. Additionally, these journals are

published by Egyptian Ministry of Agriculture, or Islamic Azad University of Iran, and are quite creditable.

Updating the checklists is necessary in order to provide researchers with the species diversity of a taxon in various regions of the world, and on the other hand, the species that were previously reported from an area, are not introduced again as new records [e.g., *Psilocera obscura* Walker, 1833 and *Stinoplus etearchus* (Walker, 1848)) had been recorded by Ghahari *et al.* (2015) and Sakenin *et al.* (2008a), respectively, but were reported again as new country records by Rahmani *et al.* (2020b)].

Additionally, Rahmani *et al.* (2022) prepared an incomplete checklist on the Middle East and North African Pteromalidae, while numerous published papers in those countries were not considered and cited. It is great to follow the example of other researchers who published on the Middle East fauna, but in order to preparing a comprehensive checklist, it is necessary to review carefully all the papers, books and other published scientific sources related to the subject.

Finally, the pteromalid species reported by H. Ghahari (In his previous published works), in addition to being previously identified or confirmed by the authorized specialists, but some of doubtful specimens were re-examined by the experts (H. Ghahari, pers. comm.), and thus are reliable. Therefore, regarding to the new published contributions after Gibson *et al.* (2021) and two new records of this survey, the total number of Iranian Pteromalidae reaches to 295 valid species in 124 genera (Appendix 1). Same as the catalogue of Gibson *et al.* (2021), the present updated checklist

¹ Regarding to the paper Abd-Rabou *et al.* (2005b), after receiving V. Mauss's agreement, a large parcel included several Vespidae and Apoidea specimens was sent to him in 2004 to

be identified by him, M. Ohl and T. Osten, but have not been done so far (H. Ghahari, pers. comm.).

comprises only the known species (Not genera with unidentified species); so, six genera with unknown species (*Cea* sp., *Guancheria* sp., *Glyphognathus* sp., *Hypopteromalus* sp., *Oxysychus* sp. and *Thureonella* sp.) are not included in this checklist until determining the species name.

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First record of dryinid and mymarid (Hymenoptera: Chrysidoidea: Chalcidoidea) parasitoids in Egypt

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Abstract

Three parasitoids were recorded for the first time in Egypt. The first one, *Dryinus canariensis* Ceballos (Hymenoptera: Chrysidoidea: Dryinidae) was collected from Saint Catherine (Sinai Peninsula) region. The others, *Dicopus* sp. and *Erythmelus (Parallelaptera) funiculi* Annecke and Doutt (Hymenoptera: Chalcidoidea: Mymaridae) were collected from Sakha (Nile Delta) region.

Introduction

Hymenopterous parasitoids are an important biological tool used widely in agriculture for the suppression of various pest species (Hagen *et al.*, 1971; DeBach, 1974 and Huffaker and Messenger, 1976). Parasitoids attack either by penetrating the body wall and laying eggs inside the host or attaching eggs to the outer body surface or attacking host eggs. The immature parasitoid develops on or within the host, consumes all or most of the host's body fluid, and pupates either within or external to the host (Hoy, 1994).

In the current study, two groups from Hymenoptera were surveyed, the first one is Dryinidae, which attacks nymph and adult species belonging to leaf and planthoppers. The second one is Mymaridae, which parasitizes the eggs of several hosts.

Dryinidae (Hymenoptera, Chrysidoidea) constitutes a family of solitary wasps with about 1,830

described species worldwide (Olm and Xu, 2015). In general, dryinids are ectoparasitoids of Auchenorrhyncha, with one nearctic/neotropical genus, *Crovettia* Olmi, being endoparasitoid of Membracidae (Olm, 1999). Females have a sting, used both as an ovipositor and for paralyzing the hosts for the time necessary for depositing the eggs. Immature larvae are ectophagous, their body is being contained in a sac or thylacium formed by the cast larval skins and protruding from the host body. They feed on the host haemolymph. Mature larvae emerge from the host body after consuming all haemolymph and internal tissues. Pupation takes place in a silk cocoon spun on plants or in the soil (Mifsud and Olmi, 2016).

Species of the family Mymaridae, are parasitic in the eggs of other insects. Mymarids are cosmopolitan in distribution and can usually be collected in large numbers (Huber, 1986). The genus *Dicopus* is

weakly known (Schauff, 1984). It belongs to the *Alaptus* group (Noyes and Valentine, 1989 and Huber, 2009).

The genus *Erythmelus* is cosmopolitan in distribution that has 54 species. It is quite common, especially in warm, dry habitats. *Erythmelus* was recorded from eggs of Heteroptera mainly Miridae, Cicadillidae and Tingidae, some of which are well-known as agricultural pests (Triapitsyn, 2003). Therefore, members of *Erythmelus* are important for classical or augmentative biological control programs against some of these pests, although they may play a much larger role as native regulators of the population densities of their hosts.

Materials and methods

1. Locations:

This work was conducted at Sakha location which has a latitude of 31° 05'.12" N and a longitude 30° 56' 56.66"E. Saint Catherine has a latitude of 28°33'33.92"N and a longitude of 33°56'48.83"E.

2. Specimens:

2.1. Dryinid specimen was collected from Saint Catherine (Sinai Peninsula) region that was identified by sweep net.

2.2. Mymarid specimens were collected during 2021 from Sakha location in Delta, Northern Egypt. The specimens were collected using three methods, blue water pan trap, malaise trap and sweep net. Specimens are deposited in the personal collection of the author at Rice Research and Training Center (RRTC) Entomology lab, Sakha, Kafr El-Sheikh, Egypt.

3. Parasitoid identification:

3.1. Dryinid specimen, *Dryinus canariensis* Ceballos (Dryinidae: Chrysidoidea) was identified by Prof. Massimo Olmi.

3.2. Mymarid parasitoids were identified by the authors of the current study. The mymarid egg parasitoids, were identified according to all taxonomic papers mentioned in this manuscript and confirmed by Prof., Serguei V. Triapitsyn, John T. Huber and Emilian Pricop.

Results and discussion

1. Family: Dryinidae

Subfamily: Dryiniinae

Dryinus canariensis (Ceballos), 1927

Material: One female was collected by sweep net.

Hosts: Unknown

Distribution: Palaearctic region: Canary Islands and St. Catherin, Sinai, Egypt.

Ceballos (1927) recorded *Dryinus canariensis* as a *Paradryinus canariensis*, Olmi (1984) put genus a new comb (*Dryinus*).

D. canariensis female: fully winged; length 4,25- 4,50 mm; head, antennae, prothorax, legs reddish; mesothorax, metathorax, propodeum and petiole black; abdomen brown, with segment 1 reddish as Olmi (1984) mentioned (Figure 1). Fore tarsal segments in following proportions: 15: 4: 7: 15: 24; enlarged claw with a subapical tooth and with 12 lamellae; segment 5 of front tarsus with 2 rows of nearly 27 lamellae same length; apex with a group of 12 lamellae as Olmi (1984) mentioned (Figure 1).

Female of *Dryinus canariensis*

Chela

Wing after Ceballos (1927)

Chela after Olmi (1984)

Figure (1): *Dryinus canariensis* (Ceballos), 1927

2. Family: Mymaridae

2.1. Genus: *Dicopus* Enock

Material: One female

Hosts: Unknown

Distribution: worldwide.

Twelve species have been described worldwide: *Dicopus minutissimus* Enock and *D. cervus* Morley from the United Kingdom; *D. citri* Mercet from Spain; *D. halitus* Girault from Canada (Quebec); *D. enocki* Doutt and *D. pygmaeus* Doutt from the USA (California); *D. longipes* (Subba Rao) and *D. noyesi* Manickavasagam from India; *D. bidentiscapus* Girault from Australia (Victoria); *D. psyche* Girault from Fiji

and *D. lilliput* Mathot from The Democratic Republic of Congo (Zaire); *D. moscovit* Triapitsyn from Russia all species are listed in Noyes (2014).

Specimen was collected during 2021 from Sakha location in Delta, Northern Egypt using blue water pan trap. *Dicopus* is characterized by the following combination of characters (Figure 2): according to many authors; Doutt, 1974; Schauff, 1984; Yoshimoto, 1990; Huber, 1997; Viggiani, 2003; Huber 2009; Manickavasagam and Rameshkumar, 2011; Pricop and Ndriescu, 2011 and Triapitsyn, 2015.

Front and hind wings

Antenna

Genitalia

***Dicopus* sp.**

Figure (2): *Dicopus* sp.

2.2. Genus: *Erythmelus* Enock

Subgenus: *Parallelaptera*

Erythmelus (Parallelaptera) funiculi

Annecke and Doutt, 1961

Material examined: 2 females, the first specimen was collected by malaise trap on 16th of July, 2021, and the second one was collected by sweep net on 7th of September, 2021, both females were collected from graminaceous weeds infested by many kinds of cicadellids at Sakha Agricultural Research Station.

Diagnosis: *E. funiculi* is a very distinctive species due to the proportions of funicle segments of the female antenna: F3, which bears two

longitudinal sensilla, is much longer than F2 or F4 and almost as long as F5 (Figure 3) (Annecke and Doutt, 1961 and Triapitsyn, 2003). This species is known from the female only (Triapitsyn, 2003).

Distribution: South Africa (Annecke and Doutt, 1961), Uganda (Triapitsyn, 1993), USA (Hawaiian Islands) (Beardsley and Huber, 2000) and Egypt.

Host: Unknown.

E. (Parallelaptera) funiculi is a very rare species from mymarids, and Sakha region is the only location where it was found in Egypt till now.

Front wing

Antenna

Females

Figure (3): *Erythmelus (Paralleleptera) funiculi* Annecke and Doutt

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Impact of some chemical pesticides against the glassy clover snail *Monacha cartusiana* (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae) adults and their effects on genotoxicity

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Abstract

Toxicological studies disclosed that the molluscicidal activity of chemical pesticides, i.e., Methomyl, avaut, pestban, and herbazed against the glassy clover snail, *Monacha cartusiana* (O. F. Müller) (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae) adults using the poisonous baits technique under laboratory conditions. Comparative toxicity indicated that methomyl was the most impact compound followed, with avaut, pestban and herbazed pesticides. The mortality percentages were increasing with augmenting the concentrations of tested pesticides and times of exposure. Comparing the toxicity action of the four tested pesticides based on toxicity index, methomyl was considered as the standard pesticide recorded 100%, while a toxicity index values of avaut, pestban, and herbazed for LC₅₀ and LC₉₀ were (70.00 ,57.19 and 53.00) and (65.26, 60.19 and 57.89), respectively. Finally, data indicated that all tested pesticides reasoned augmentation in DNA damage, tail length, DNA in tail, tail moment and olive tail moment. Methomyl was the most pesticide that caused increasing in DNA damage of target cells (17.58%), while avaut caused 15.61% subordinate by pestban and herbazed with 11.60 and 10.59%, respectively compared with control (7.35%).

Introduction

Mollusks studied that diverse many distinguished lineages of terrestrial gastropods and belong to the second- biggest phylum next arthropods in terms of number of species. Terrestrial mollusks have been exceeded greatly worldwide while forming about 6% of total species on earth and else showing economic importance (Clark and May, 2002). Land mollusks became one of the most dangerous pests attacking numerous plants (Shahawy, 2019). The devastating likelihood of these pests

is far better today than in previous times as an effect of ever denser and faster transport and traffic (Godan, 1983; Ali and Suleman, 1992 and Barker, 2002).

Newly, in Egypt, land snails have been considered a dangerous pest that attaches several crops, i.e., Vegetables, cereals, fruit gardens, and decorative plants at the diverse growth stages causing a decrease in the production of these yields. Moreover, a land snail in some crops is now becoming evident with a reduction in the consequences of other pest groups

such as insects. Besides, the locomotion of snails causes unsolicited odor by secreting viscid liquids on the plants preventing men and field animals from feeding on this contaminated plant (Kassab and Daoud, 1964; El-Okda, 1984 and Sallam *et al.*, 2009).

The glassy clover snail, *Monacha cartusiana* (O. F. Müller) (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae) is deemed the most predominant snail in several governorates in Egypt, and many authors reported a relatively high incidence and population density of *Monacha* spp. in Sharkia Governorate (Ismail, 1997; Hegab *et al.*, 1999 and Mahrous *et al.*, 2002). Traditional pesticides especially carbamates and organophosphorus compounds are effectively used in Egypt just as in many nations as spray or baits (Heiba *et al.*, 2002). So, both were applied, methomyl is one of the strong carbamates utilized especially in bait methods towards terrestrial gastropods and pestban as an organophosphorus compound was found to actuate oxidative stress and affect some biochemical targets in snails (Salama *et al.*, 2005).

Regarding, Avaunt is a novel pesticide that belongs to the oxadiazine pesticides group which acts on the target organism as a sodium channel blocker (Shono *et al.*, 2004). Finally, herbazed pesticide is used as herbicide in the laboratory using the baits technique. So, linking the reactions due to these pesticides with the progress of these compounds with the physiological system (Schlenk, 1999).

The main goal of the present work is to study the following points: Evaluation of the toxicity impact of some pesticides belonging to the different groups towards *M. cartusiana* adults under laboratory conditions and determined comet assay as geneotoxicity of tested pesticides.

Materials and methods

1. Examined animal:

Land snail, the glassy clover snail, *M. cartusiana* adults needed for the present trails were collected from a farm cultivated with Egyptian clover, *Trifolium alexandrinum* L. at Sharkia Governorate, Egypt. Individuals were immediately transferred in white cloth bags to the laboratory. Healthy and similar snails were select and kept in glass terrarium filled with wet mud soil amended at 75% of water field capacity. Snails were fed daily with bran for two weeks before treatment for acclimation.

2. Examined chemical pesticides:

Pesticides were methomyl 90% S.P. (Trade name), lannate (common name), S-methyl-N- {(methyl carbamoyl) oxy} thioacetimidate (chemical name). Pestban 48% E.C. (Trade name), chlorpyrifos (common name), Chlorpyrifos (O, O-Diethyl O-3,5,6-trichloropyridin-2-pyridinyl) phosphorothioate (chemical name). Avaunt 15% E.C. (Trade name), indoxacarb (common name), S-methyl -7-chloro-2,4,4a,5-tetrahydro-4a-(methoxycarbonyl) indeno[1,2-e][1,3,4] oxadiazia-2-carbonyl]-4-(trifluoromethoxy) carboxylate (chemical name). Finally, Herbazed 48% W.C. (Trade name), glyphosate (common name) N-(phosphonomethyl) glycine, isopropyl amminoum salt (chemical name).

3. Toxicity studies:

The present search was achieved at laboratory of Plant Protection Research Institute to research the influence of some pesticides which belonging to different chemical groups against the land snail, *M. cartusiana*, adults using baits technique.

4. Toxic baits technique:

Baits were designed by mixing five concentrations (2.00, 1.00, 0.5, 0.25 and 0.125%) of each tested compound merged with five parts of molasses then finished with wheat

bran to 100 parts and wetted with small amounts of water (Ghamry *et al.*, 1994). Three replicates of plastic boxes (3/4 kg capacity) were utilized for each concentration of pesticide; Five g of each toxic bait were spread into each box. Three plastic boxes (3/4 kg capacity) were utilized for each concentration. 5 g of each toxic bait was spread into each box.

Control treatment was designed using bran bait. Five adult individuals of snails were put into each plastic box, then enveloped with muslin cloth and secured with rubber band. Daily examination was carried out for treatments by utilization stainless steel needle (El-Okda, 1981).

The dead snails were secluded daily, and mortality percentages were registered until the 28 days after treatment. The average of mortality percentages of each component was corrected utilization Abbott's (1925) formula. LC_{50} and LC_{90} values were calculated utilization (BioStat, 2007) (Professional Build 3200).

Toxicity index (T.I) was determined utilization formula of Sun (1950) Neutralization as follows: Toxicity index = $[\frac{LC_{50} \text{ or } LC_{90} \text{ of the highest efficient compound}}{LC_{50} \text{ or } LC_{90} \text{ of the other compound}}] \times 100$.

Relative potency (R.P) was determined utilization formula of Zidan and Abdel-Maged (1988) Neutralization as follows: Relative potency (R.P.) = $[\frac{LC_{50} \text{ or } LC_{90} \text{ of the other compound}}{LC_{50} \text{ or } LC_{90} \text{ of the highest efficient compound}}]$.

5. Genotoxicity of pesticides:

Comet assay:

The tissues of *M. cartusiana*, adult processed with LC_{25} of pesticides was utilized after three days of treatment for the alkaline comet assay according to Singh *et al.* (1988). For each sample of pesticide, 100 incidentally opted cells were depicted

and scanned for picture analysis. The cells with short heads and big fan-like tails were an exemption. The pictures were analyzed utilization the comet score analysis method for each cell, the length of DNA emigration (Tail length) was measured on Pixel from the center of the nucleus to the end of the tail, DNA percentage in the tail was measured wherein the total intensity (Fluorescence) in the cells, which was delimited as 100%, and the percentage of total intensity collimated to the intensity just in the tail was rimmed. The tail moment explained in arbitrary units was computable as $(\text{Tail length} \times \% \text{ migrated DNA}) / 100$.

6. Statistical analysis:

The statistical analysis was limited by utilizing one way test, (ANOVA), Cohort Software (2005).

Results and discussion

1. Toxicological studies under laboratory conditions:

1.1. Accumulation mortality percentage of *Monacha cartusiana* adults exposed to numerous chemical pesticides using baits technique:

Results in Table (1) reported that toxicity influence of tested pesticides, methomyl, avaut, pestban, and herbazed against *M. cartusiana* adults. Data studied that methomyl (2%) due to mortality with percentages 100% after 28 days post-treatment, while at concentration 1% caused 40% mortality after the first day to reach its maximum effect than 14 days with that 100%. At a concentration of 0.5% remarked after one day with 20% to record 100% mortality percentage at 21st day. While, Avaunt initiated its initial impact after one week at concentration 2% with mortality percentage (86.67%) to achieve 100% mortality till the end of exposure snails, but at concentration of 1%, the mortality percentage rates acquired after 7, and 28 days were 53.33 and 100%. At concentration 0.25% mortality percentages and were (13.33,

20.00,40.00, 53.33, and 66.67%) post 3, 7, 14, 21 and 28 days post-treatment, inversion to concentration of 0.125% which have slightest impact and recording for 7 day without any impact and increased until 28 day with 33.33%.

Regarded to pestban efficiency after 14 days of exposure gave 100% mortality of treatment at 2% concentration, to come with 40% mortality percentage on 7th day then killed all snails post 21st and 28th day when used to 1% of concentration.

Table (1): Accretive mortality percentage of *Monacha cartusiana* adults exposed to varied chemical compounds using baits technique.

Tested materials	Conc. %	Accretive mortality / day						Mean mortality
		1	3	7	14	21	28	
Methomyl	0.125	0.00	0.00	13.33	26.67	33.33	40.00	18.89 ^{kl}
	0.25	0.00	13.33	33.33	40.00	66.67	73.33	37.77 ^{hi}
	0.5	20.00	26.67	53.33	73.33	100.00	100.00	62.22 ^{de}
	1.0	40.00	53.33	86.67	100.00	100.00	100.00	80.00 ^{bc}
	2.0	73.33	86.67	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	93.33 ^a
Avaunt	0.125	0.00	0.00	0.00	13.33	26.67	33.33	12.22 ^{kl}
	0.25	0.00	13.33	20.00	40.00	53.33	66.67	32.22 ^{ij}
	0.5	13.33	26.67	33.33	73.33	93.33	93.33	55.55 ^{ef}
	1.0	26.67	40.00	53.33	100.00	100.00	100.00	70.00 ^{cd}
	2.0	53.33	73.33	86.67	100.00	100.00	100.00	85.56 ^{ab}
Pestban	0.125	0.00	0.00	0.00	13.33	26.67	33.33	12.22 ^{kl}
	0.25	0.00	6.67	13.33	33.33	46.67	53.33	25.55 ^{jk}
	0.5	6.67	13.33	26.67	53.33	73.33	86.67	43.33 ^{gh}
	1.0	13.33	26.67	40.00	86.67	100.00	100.00	61.11 ^{de}
	2.0	33.33	53.33	86.67	100.00	100.00	100.00	78.89 ^{bc}
Herbazed	0.125	0.00	0.00	0.00	6.67	13.33	13.33	5.55 ^l
	0.25	0.00	0.00	6.67	20.00	26.67	26.67	13.34 ^{kl}
	0.5	0.00	6.67	20.00	33.33	46.67	53.33	26.67 ^{jk}
	1.0	13.33	20.00	33.33	53.33	73.33	93.33	47.77 ^{fg}
	2.0	20.00	33.33	66.67	86.67	100.00	100.00	67.78 ^{cd}
Control		0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00 ^l
P		0.0001***	0.0001***	0.0001***	0.0001***	0.0001***	0.0001***	0.0001***
L.S.D.0.05		12.46	9.28	9.59	9.29	8.30	8.31	19.55

At 0.5% concentration the mortality percentages were (6.67, 13.33, 26.67, 53.33, 73.33 and 86.67%) after 1, 3, 7, 14, 21, and 28 days, respectively. For 0.25% concentration small effect happened begging from the third day, with percentage mortality of 6.67%, to be noticed after two weeks, by percentage mortality 33.33%, to reason its highest effectiveness after 28th the day of exposure with percentage 53.33%. While, Data not recorded any mortality until the 7th the day when processe d *M. cartusiana* adult was treated with 0.125%,

to occur its impact, then 28 days with a percentage of 33.33 %. In connection with, herbazed, it existed constant at 66.67% for one week of treatment which was observed with 100% mortality percentage after 21and 28 days of exposure with 2% of concentration. At a concentration of 1% attained mortality percentages of 33.33% after 7 days, but after 21 and 28 days, it was reported with mortality percentages (73.33 and 93.33%), respectively. Regard to herbazed at a concentration of 0.5% gave mortality percentage with (20%) post 7day and after

28 days of treatment noticed with 53.33%. Herbazed at a concentration of 0.25%, noticed in constant death rates from 21 days until 28 days, also at a concentration of 0.125% with mortality with percentage (13.33%) for the same time of exposure. These outcomes were similar with Tribskorn and Ebert (1989) reported that increasing the concentration of methomyl pesticide and time elapsed due to increase the mortality percent of juveniles and adults. The carbamate, methomyl noticed with the highest toxic action against *M. cartusiana* snail followed by the marshal and dursban, respectively (Daoud, 2004). Ebenso *et al.* (2005) reported *Limicolaria aurora*, snail desistance feeding post-treatment with methomyl and furadan. At a concentration of 1%, methomyl was 92.5% mortality of *M. cartusiana* after 28 days of treatment El-Shafiey *et al.* (2010). Also, Shetaia *et al.* (2013), noticed that methomyl was the most potent compound in the laboratory for controlled *M. cartusiana*. Ismail *et al.* (2022) studied that the impression of methomyl pesticide was increased as the concentration was increased in all treatments against some land snails *M. cartusiana*, *Succinea putris* and *Eobania vermiculata*. Also, it is clear from the results that *M. cartusiana* was the most sensibility for tested pesticide using the baits technique.

1.2. Comparative toxicity of methomyl, avaut, pestban and herbazed as pesticides against adult of *Monacha cartusiana* snail using baits technique:

The tested pesticides could be arranged according to their ability against snail were (1436.40 ±14.12 and 3013.60 ±39.90), (2061± 24.60 and 4617.58 ±10.72), (2511.20 ± 28.15 and 5006.00 ±11.03) and (2710.60 ±25.13 and 5205.50±14.12) µg/ml, for methomyl, avaut, pestban and herbazed, respectively. Comparing the toxicity

action of the four tested toxicants based on toxicity index, methomyl was considered as the standard insecticide and registering 100%, while a toxicity index value of avaut, pestban, and herbazed for LC₅₀ and LC₉₀ were (70.00 ,57.19 and 53.00%) and (65.26, 60.19 and 57.89%), respectively. The LC₅₀, LC₉₀, relative potency and toxicity index values were presented in Table (2) and Figure (1) whereas, methomyl was the most efficient compound followed by avaut, pestban, while herbazed was the least once. Relative potency level can also be utilized as the easy method in comparing the degree of toxicity of different pesticides to any pest, where potency level was acquired by dividing the LC₅₀ and LC₉₀ of herbazed, which rated as the standard compound at LC₅₀ and LC₉₀ levels, by the corresponding Figure (1) of each tested pesticide. At LC₅₀ level the relative potency levels expressed as the number of fold mention that methomyl, avaut, and pestban were impact against tested snail which recorded (1.98, 1.31 and 1.07 fold) than herbazed (1.00), respectively while, at LC₉₀ the relative potency level was (1.72, 1.13, and 1.04 fold) for methomyl, avaut, and pestban, respectively. The previously mentioned data concurred with Aioub *et al.* (2000) reported that the carbamate compounds reason the most amazing effect contrasted with organophosphours, while the herbicides were the least toxicant against two types of snail, *Eobania vermiculata* (O. F. Müller) (Gastropoda: Helicidae) and *M. cartusiana* treatment with some pesticides such as; oxamyl, malathion, pirimphs-methyl, profenofos, isoproturon and tralkoxydim under laboratory conditions. Bailey (2002) suggested

that carbamates are considered feeding inhibitors. On the other hand, the LC₅₀ value of dursban pesticide was 3.69 and 4.73% for *M. cartusiana* and *E. vermiculata*, respectively (Zedan *et al.* 2006). Carbofuran pesticide was the most toxic compound against *M. obstructa* adults whereas its LC₅₀ value was 0.18% followed by methomyl 0.39%, pyriproxyfen 0.49%, benthio carb 0.90% and fenthion 1.54% while dicofol

pesticide was the lowest effective one; its LC₅₀ value was 4.05% (Gabr *et al.* 2007). Also, Ali (2017) studied that the newly pesticide which belongs to the carbamates group was the most potent one followed by thymol as monoterpenes or katrothriul as pyrethroid and round up as an organophosphorus when control of *M. cartusiana* adult using baits and leaf dipping technique under laboratory.

Table (2): Comparative toxicity of chemical compounds against adult of *Monacha cartusiana*, snail using baits technique.

Treatments (µg/ml)	Adult of <i>Monacha cartusiana</i>						
	LC ₅₀	LC ₉₀	Slope	Toxicity index		Relative potency	
				LC ₅₀	LC ₉₀	LC ₅₀	LC ₉₀
Methomyl	1436.4±14.12	3013.6±39.9	1.4	100	100	1.98	1.72
Avaunt	2061±24.6	4617.58±10.72	1.6	70.00	65.26	1.31	1.13
Pestban	2511.2±28.15	5006.00±11.03	2.45	57.19	60.19	1.07	1.04
Herbazed	2710.6±25.13	5205.5±14.12	3.6	53.00	57.89	1.00	1.00

Figure (1): Toxicity regression line of some chemical compounds using baits technique against adult of *Monacha cartusiana*, snail.

2. Genotoxicology studies of *Monacha cartusiana*, adult:

Comet assay:

This research studied to identify potential geneotoxicity as comet assay, also to realize as the single-cell gel

electrophoresis (SCGE) assay, is comprehensively applied as one of the standard ways to valuating DNA damage triggered through a range of DNA destructive agents in eukaryotic cells may be measured.

It depends on the quantification of the distortion and DNA fragments departing out of the cell nucleus during electrophoresis. This assay has obtained large-scale utilize in various areas including human bio monitoring, genotoxicology, ecological monitoring, and as an instrument for research into DNA damage or repair in different cell types.

Table (3) indicated that some standards checked in the hemolymph of *M. cartusiana* adult after three days of treatment with methomyl, avaut, pestban and herbazed pesticides at (LC25) by baits technique, where the data showed that all tested materials reasoned increasing in DNA damage, tail length, DNA in tail, tail moment and olive tail moment. Methomyl was the most pesticide which reasoned augmentation in DNA damage in target cells (17.58%), while avaut caused 15.61% subordinate by pestban and herbazed with 11.60 and 10.59% compared with control (7.35%).

Also, a high increasing was recorded in tail length (TL) 14.39, 13.75, 12.77 and 7.76 μm post exposure to methomyl, avaut, pestban and herbazed, respectively compared control 6.80 μm . For DNA in tail, methomyl due to significant rising and observed with (12.70%) compared

with herbazed which observed with least impact (6.92%). Moreover, the present data appeared augmentation in tail moment (TL) and olive tail moment (OMT) than control, and recorded with (1.05, 0.94, 0.86 and 0.77%) and (2.52, 1.95, 1.80, and 1.16%) for methomyl, avaut, pestban and herbazed, respectively.

Comet were divided into four class (0-3) according to the extent of DNA immigration, comet with bright heads and no visibly tail was assigned as class 0, comet with very meager heads and long extendedly tails class 3, comets exhibited traits mediator between class 0 and 3 divide and earmarked to easily notable class 1 and 2 (Figure 2).

Also, DNA migration was valuation using visible scoring and pictures analysis is precise in the measurability of DNA damage, forgiveness to measure the fluorescence severity and distribution of DNA by the comet assay. In the visible scoring a numeric index is ordinarily user to symbolize the average DNA migration according to Burlinson *et al.* (2007). Also, similar observations obtained that Itziou *et al.* (2011) revealed that chlorpyrifos and parathion-methyl due to the highest damage in DNA of *E. vermiculata* snail digestive gland.

Table (3): Comet assay test for *M. cartusiana*, adult exposure to sub-lethal concentration (LC25) of methomyl, Avaut, Pestban and Herbazed.

Tested materials	DNA damage (%)	Tail length (μm)	DNA in tail (%)	Tail moment	Olive tail moment
Methomyl	17.58 \pm 0.31** *	14.39 \pm 0.28** *	12.70 \pm 0.22** *	1.05 \pm 0.015** *	2.52 \pm 0.062** *
Avaut	15.61 \pm 0.21** *	13.75 \pm 0.20** *	10.61 \pm 0.15** *	0.94 \pm 0.008** *	1.95 \pm 0.023** *
Pestban	11.60 \pm 0.60** *	12.77 \pm 0.11** *	9.70 \pm 0.91***	0.86 \pm 0.014** *	1.80 \pm 0.027** *
Herbazed	10.59 \pm 0.12** *	7.76 \pm 0.14* *	6.92 \pm 0.47***	0.77 \pm 0.03***	1.16 \pm 0.045** *
Control	7.35 \pm 0.18***	6.80 \pm 0.10***	3.56 \pm 0.18***	0.58 \pm 0.00***	0.41 \pm 0.056** *

Data expressed as Mean \pm Stander error; P >0.005.

Figure (2): DNA content integrity via comet bioassay:

a) Control group showing undamaged DNA without comet tail, (Class 0).

b) Methomyl treatment showing an appearance of major damaged DNA (Class 3).

c, d) Avaunt and Pestban treatments showing an appearance of moderate damaged DNA (Class 2).

e) Herbazed treatment showing an appearance of heterogeneity of comet tail length (Class 0 and Class 2). (x.,400).

Mohamed *et al.* (2013) reported that atrazine and glyphosate as herbicides have a high impact on genotoxicants agents of *Biomphalaria glabrata* (Say) (Planorbidae: Gastropoda) snail. This proved the ability of these compounds to cause change inside *M. cartusiana* cells by using low concentrations with the baits technique. Guanggang *et al.* (2013) studied that methomyl at sub-lethal concentration has a significant influence on DNA damage, whereas reasoned increasing in the tail length, tail DNA and tail moment *in vitro* compared with control of *Drosophila* insect. Ibrahim *et al.* (2018) reported that DNA damage is a serious biomarker of toxicity in snails. Al-Fanharawi *et al.* (2019) indicated that CPF (Chlorpyrifos) at concentrations 15, 22, and 45 mg/l due to an increase in comet length, tail length, and tail moment in the digestive gland of the snail *Viviparous bengalensis*

(Lamarck) (Mesogastropoda : Viviparidae) . Finally, Gaber *et al.* (2022) reported the toxic impact of two sub-lethal concentrations of methomyl pesticide LC₂₀ (0.075 g / L) and LC₄₀ (0.180 g / L) on some biochemical parameters and histological for *M. cartusiana* snail.

The presented data reported that using some methomyl, avaunt, pestban and herbazed pesticides against the glassy clover snail, *M. cartusiana* adults. Results found that the accretive mortality percentage was increased progressively by raising the exposure time and concentration. Half lethal concentrations (LC₅₀) and toxicity index of different tested pesticides were evaluated; the compounds tested could be arranged to descend as methomyl, avaunt, pestban and herbazed, respectively according to their LC₅₀ and toxicity index. Also, data was studied that all tested

pesticides have the ability for damaging DNA of *M. cartusiana*, treated with LC25 at three days compared with the control.

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Efficacy of gallic oil extract (*Allium sativum*) and its nano emulsion on mortality and physiology of cotton leaf worm *Spodoptera littoralis* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae)

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Abstract

The cotton leaf worm *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) is a major insect pest attacks a large-scale economic crop, there are many different ways to control this pest using chemicals and essential oils. Chemical pesticides are most effective, but they cause pollution to humans, plants and the environment. One of these essential oils is garlic oil and its nano emulsion that is used in the presented study to evaluate the mortality of second instar larvae. Also, physiological tests were conducted on the fourth instar larvae of cotton leaf worm. The results of the mortality test showed the effectiveness of nano emulsion of garlic oil more than the bulk garlic oil with LC₅₀ 56 ppm however LC₅₀ for garlic oil was 7633.58 ppm. While the physiological test is done for estimating acid phosphates, alkaline phosphates and digestive enzymes (Lipase), and the results showed that the control experiments were 176 u/L, 185 u/L and 49.7u/L, respectively. on the other hands, garlic oil extract showed 97.5U/L,133 U/L and 38 U/L respectively and garlic oil nano emulsion showed 150 U/L,164U/L and 39 U/L, respectively.

Introduction

The Egyptian cotton leaf worm *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) is one of the most important insect pests which feed on the crops (Azab *et al.*, 2001), the application of conventional pesticides led to insecticide resistance (Saleem *et al.*, 2008). Currently, insecticides are used to control cotton leaf worm infestation which is harmful to humans and animals.

Presently insecticides are used to control insect pest infestation that caused hazardous to animals and humans (Ismail and Shaker, 2014). Many plants have natural substances

that can be used to control insect pests and these plants have a deleterious effect in several manners like toxicity, mortality, antifeedants growth inhibitor, suppression of reproductive behavior, and reduction of fecundity and fertility (Jbilou *et al.*, 2006 and Hamada *et al.*, 2018).

Garlic oil contains some Sulphur-containing compounds (Aliin, ajoene, allicin, diallyl 1 trisulphide, dithin, sallylcysteine), enzymes, minerals (Mg, Zn, Se and Ge), vitamins (C, A, B complex), amino acids, proteins, saponins and flavonoids (Block, 1992 and Johnson *et al.*, 2013) therefore, garlic essential oil was

reported to have insecticidal effects on pests of stored products (Ho *et al.*, 1996 and Moawad and Sadek, 2018). Trying to use garlic oil as nano emulsion, could have a beneficial effect on pest management.

The aim of this study is to compare the impact of garlic oil and its nano emulsion on cotton leaf worm under laboratory conditions and to determine the effect of these substances on physiology analysis of cotton leaf worm.

Materials and methods

1. Tested cotton leaf worm:

A laboratory strain of *S. littoralis* was reared under constant conditions of 27±2°C, photoperiod of 14 hrs. light and 10 hrs. dark and 65±5% R.H. Larvae were fed on castor leaves that were used at second instar for laboratory experiments.

1.1. Tested oils:

1.1.1. Garlic oil (Essential oil)

1.1.2. Garlic oil (Nano emulsion)

1.2. Preparation and isolation of essential garlic plant oil:

Essential garlic oil was extracted from the clover of the garlic plant and extracted by steam distillation apparatus that was found in Plant Protection Institute, Mansoura, Egypt. Separated oil was dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate and stored in dark glass bottles at 4° C in a refrigerator until used.

1.3. Preparation of nano emulsions of garlic oil:

The method of preparation of was described by Jerobin *et al.* (2012) garlic oil was diluted with distilled water in a ratio of 1:1 (Oil to water), and Tween 80 was added as an emulsifier. Then, the emulsion was sonicated for 30 minutes using the ultrasonic cleaner set (Model WUC-DO3H 290W) at 60 Hz. Also, it was resonicated for 1

minute using high energy the ultrasonication probe (model VCX750) set to 750W and 20 kHz, and then it was resonated again by the ultrasonic cleaner set under cooling conditions for 30 minutes (Youssef *et al.*, 2018).

1.4. Preparation of the stock solution of the tested materials:

Concentrations of garlic oil and the Nano-emulsion of garlic oil were prepared on basis of the tested material weight and the volume of the distilled water (w/v). Tween 80 (0.1%) was used as an emulsifier. The stock concentrations were kept in glass stoppered bottles and stored under refrigeration. Such stock solutions were prepared periodically. Five diluted concentrations were used to draw the LC-P Lines for each material and four replicates were used for each concentration.

1.5. Larvicidal activity of tested oil (Essential and nano):

To determine the toxicity action of the tested materials, 2nd larval instar was used. The castor bean leaf discs were dipped into the treatments for 20 seconds and then left for air dryness. Ten larvae for each replicate were released to each leaf disc placed. The used concentrations were 500, 1000, 5000, 7500 and 10000 ppm (for garlic oil), however, the concentrations were 40, 80, 100, 250 and 500 ppm for garlic oil nano emulsion. The same number of leaf discs was dipped into dis. water as an untreated check. The percentage of mortality was recorded after one day, three days, five days and seven days. Data were corrected relatively to control mortality (Abbott, 1925). LC₅₀ and LC₉₀ values were determined using the probit analysis statistical method of (Finney, 1971 and Sun, 1950 equation) (Used to determine LC₅₀ index).

$$\text{Toxicity Index for LC}_{50} = \frac{\text{LC}_{50} \text{ of the most effective compound}}{\text{LC}_{50} \text{ of the least effective compound}} \times 100$$

2. Physiological analysis:

In this presented study, 4th instar larvae of cotton leaf worm were used for this purpose. Acid phosphates (ACP) and alkaline phosphates (ALT) were determined according to the method described by Powell and Smith (1954), on the other hand, aspirated amino transaminase was determined according to the method of Reitman and Frankle (1957).

Results and discussion

1. Efficiency of garlic oil and nano emulsion against leave of *Spodoptera littoralis*:

Data in Table (1) demonstrated that, the concentration 500 ppm of nano emulsion was the highest concentration that caused the highest mortality rate 90%, moreover the highest concentration of garlic oil 10000 ppm caused 66.67% mortality rate. The rest of nano emulsion concentrations were 40, 80, 100 and 250 ppm caused mortality rate 40%, 53.33%, 73.33%, 80%, respectively. Otherwise, garlic oil concentrations were 500, 1000, 5000, 7500 ppm notated 10%, 16.67%, 30%, 46.67 and 66.67%, respectively. The obtained results agreed with Hashem *et al.* (2020) who evaluated the toxic effect of aniseed (*Pimpinella anisum* L.) essential oil and its nano emulsion against the red flour beetle *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst) (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae) and proved that the nano emulsion has the highest effect than the essential oil. In addition, Marouf *et al.* (2021) tested the efficacy of

camphor oil and its nano emulsion against *S. littoralis* and proved that the nano emulsion has the highest effect than the essential oil these results agreed with the presented data. Furthermore, data in Table (2) and Figure (1) indicated that, LC₅₀ of nano emulsion of garlic oil is lower than LC₅₀ of bulk garlic oil which recorded 56 ppm for nano emulsion but the garlic oil recorded 7633.58 ppm. This means that, nano emulsion of garlic oil is more efficient than garlic oil. These results were in agreement with Dimetry *et al.* (2019) and Ebeid (2020) who indicated the efficiency of nano emulsions of some essential oils against *S. littoralis* and *Agrotis ipsilon* (Hufnagel) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) than the bulk essential oils. At the same time, LC₉₀ showed the efficiency of nano emulsion than the essential garlic oil and recorded 469.91 and 98082.88 ppm for nano emulsion of garlic oil and bulk garlic oil, respectively. The toxicity index was 100% for the nano emulsion while it was 0.73 for bulk garlic oil. Moreover, Table (2) and Figure (1) showed that, slope values were 1.39 & 1.16 for nano emulsion and the essential garlic oil, respectively. Also, LC₉₀/LC₅₀ values were 12.8 and 08.4 for garlic essential oil and nano emulsion, respectively. This means that, the highest slope value or the lowest LC₉₀/LC₅₀ means the steepest line of toxicity (El-Shewy, 2018) and Hashem *et al.* (2020) proved the effectiveness of nano emulsion of jojoba oil than its bulk essential oil against *A. ipsilon*.

Table (1): Mortality % of 2nd instar larvae of the cotton leaf worm, *Spodoptera littoralis* treated with garlic oil and its nano emulsion under laboratory conditions.

Treatments	Conc. (ppm)	Mortality after treatments %				Total Mortality %
		One day	Three days	Five days	Seven days	
Garlic oil	500	----	-----	3.33	6.67	10
	1000	-----	3.33	6.67	6.67	16.67
	5000	3.33	10	10	6.67	30
	7500	6.67	10	20	10	46.67
	10000	6.67	20	26.67	13.33	66.67
Garlic oil Nano emulsion	40	-----	10	13.33	16.67	40
	80	3.33	16.67	20	13.33	53.33
	100	6.67	23.33	26.67	16.67	73.33
	250	10	30	20	20	80
	500	10	30	36.67	13.33	90

Table (2): Efficiency of some plant active ingredients against 2nd instar larvae of the cotton leaf worm *Spodoptera littoralis*.

Treatments	Conc.	Corrected mortality%	LC ₅₀	LC ₉₀	Slope± S.D.	Toxicity index LC ₅₀	LC ₉₀ /LC ₅₀
Garlic oil	500	10	7633.58	98082.88	1.16± 0.13	0.73	12.8
	1000	16.67					
	5000	30					
	7500	46.67					
	10000	66.67					
Garlic oil Nano-emulsion	40	40	56	469.91	1.39± 0.17	100	8.4
	80	53.33					
	100	73.33					
	250	80					
	500	90					

R: Regression

P: Probability

Figure (1): Slope values for nano emulsion and essential oil.

2. Efficacy of garlic oil and its nano emulsion on physiology of cotton leaf worm, *Spodoptera littoralis* :

Data in Table (3) evaluated the efficacy of garlic oil and its nano emulsion on physiological changes of *S. littoralis*. The obtained data was compared between control, and garlic oil and nano emulsion. Acid phosphates was recorded at 176U/L in control while it was recorded 150U/L in nano emulsion. Alkaline phosphates were recorded at 185 u/L in control despite of

nano emulsion and garlic oil recorded at 164U/L, and 133 U/L, respectively. Lipase was recorded at 49.7U/L in control even though recorded at 39 U/L in nano emulsion and 38U/L in garlic oil. Hamadah *et al.* (2016) revealed a depressed activity in the haemolymph of only newly moulted larvae and changed acid and alkaline phosphates. Anwar and Abd El-Mageed (2005) proved inhibition of ACP when *S. littoralis* was treated with some IGRs such as chlorfluazuron and flufenoxuron.

Table (3): Efficacy of garlic oil and its nano emulsion physiology of cotton leaf worm *Spodoptera littoralis* :

Analysis	Control	Garlic oil	Nano emulsion
Acid phosphates	176 u/L	97.5U/L	150 U/L
Alkaline phosphates	185 u/L	133 U/L	164U/L
Lipase	49.7u/L	38 U/L	39 U/L

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Evaluation of some natural oils and formic acid for controlling varroa mite (*Varroa destructor*) in honey bee colonies

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Abstract

Varroa destructor is a dangerous pest directly for beekeeping and indirectly for crops that require insect pollination. *V. destructor* spread from the Asian honey bee (*Apis cerana* Fabricius) to *Apis mellifera* L. (Hymenoptera : Apidae). Mites feed on haemolymph of brood and adult bees cause colony weakness, a decrease in brood and bees. The application of integrated pest management (IPM) techniques is more recent development in *V. destructor* control because its more effective than pesticides. This study was carried out to assess the efficacy of three natural oils (Camphor oil –mint oil – anise oil) and formic acid (65%) used at three concentrations (25%, 50% and 75%) against *V. destructor* in honey bee colonies (*A. mellifera*) during the period of January till September 2021 in Sidi Salem, Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate, Egypt. Data indicated that formic acid and the highest concentrations (75%) of tested essential oils caused effective control of varroa mites, whereas the infestation reduction percentage with formic acid, camphor oil recorded more than 80% after treatments on both brood and adult. while anise oil recorded the lowest one.

Introduction

The varroa mite (*Varroa destructor*) is an ectoparasitic mite on honey bee brood and adults .it considered one of the most pests in honey bee colonies (Sammataro *et al.*, 2000 and Anderson and Trueman, 2000). It causes big losses to honey bee , *Apis mellifera* L. (Hymenoptera : Apidae) and great economic loss to the worldwide beekeeping industry (Rashid *et al.*, 2012) and also, reduces the colony ability to pollinate plants (De Jong *et al.*, 1984), the varroa mite is considered as the parasite with the most pronounced economic impact on the beekeeping industry (Guzman-Novoa

et al.,2010). There is current concern about contamination of bee products with synthetic substances against the varroa (Howis and Nowakowski, 2009). The mite is an ectoparasite, that transfers entomopathogens such as viruses, thus causing death of brood and adult bees in colonies (De Jong *et al.*,1982). Natural products such as essential oils and their components or organic acids, especially formic acid and citric acid were used for controlling varroa mites (Mutinelli *et al.*,1997).

Formic acid and thymol are effective in the control of varroa mites without any side effects (Soroker *et al.*, 2019). In a similar way, smoke from

plants has produced mixed success in increasing varroa reduction. Varroa mites need to be controlled because untreated colonies collapsed within a few years due to damage to both brood and adult bees (Elzen *et al.*, 2000). In previous studies, plant essential oils have been examined and applied as alternatives to synthetic pesticides for varroa management (Rosenkranz *et al.*, 2010 and Plettner *et al.*, 2017). These circumstances allow for the development and testing of the effectiveness of new preparations (Gurgulova *et al.*, 2004). Little is known about the electrophysiological detection of essential oils and essential oil components by acarine (Soroker *et al.*, 2019).

The aim of the present study is to evaluate some natural products for controlling varroa mite on honey bees, these natural materials generally have no side effects on honey bees and are less hazardous to beekeepers.

Materials and methods

1. Experimental site:

The experiment was carried out in an apiary at Sidi Salem district, Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate during the period from January to September 2021 to study the effect of some natural products for controlling *V. destructor* in honey bee colonies. Whereas the study required eighteen colonies of carniolan hybrid nearly of equal strength. The colonies have been divided into 6 groups (Each group 3 colonies).

2. Materials:

- 2.1. Camphor oil (25%-50% -75%)
- 2.2. Mint oil (25% -50% -75%)
- 2.3. Anise oil (25% -50% -75%)
- 2.4. Formic acid (65%)

The bottom board of the hive was covered with a plastic sheet coated with Vaseline to capture the fallen mites.

3. Determination of varroa infestation:

The percent infestations of varroa mite on adult before and after treatments were determined according to Korneili (1988), whereas the number of mites\100 was calculated and the fallen varroa on the plastic sheet was counted periodically every 3 days till the end of treatment. The percent infestations of varroa mites on brood cells was determined by square inch.

Reduction percentage in mite infestation was calculated according to Henderson and Tilton (1955)

$$\text{Reduction \%} = \frac{\text{Control before} - \text{Treatment after}}{\text{Control before}} \times 100$$

4. Statistical analysis:

Data collected were statistically analyzed according to SAS Institute (1998) computer program.

Results and discussion

Three natural oils namely (Camphor oil, mint oil and anise oil) and formic acid were evaluated against *V. destructor* under field conditions. Data in Tables (1 and 2) showed that the reduction percentage of varroa mite infestation on adult was clearly reduced after the treatments in all tested oils and formic acid. In the colonies treated with essential oils and formic acid the reduction percentage of infestation with varroa on adult reduced gradually from the first treatment to the fourth (End of treatment) after the treatments. formic acid 65% and camphor oil caused a highly effective in controlling varroa mites, whereas the reduction percentage of infestation of Formic acid, camphor oil, mint oil and anise oil in January recorded (88.5%), (87.2%), (72.1%), (61.7%) after treatment on adult, respectively. Whereas, anise oil was the lowest percentage of infection reduction. The reduction percentage of infection of formic acid, camphor oil, mint oil and anise oil in September was recorded (94.5%), (89.6%), (65.3%),

(56%), respectively. The obtained data are in agreement with Allam *et al.* (2003) who found that formic acid killed 91.7% of varroa mites and Abd El-Wahab and Ebada (2006) and Hamaad *et al.* (2008) found that thyme oils resulted in 65.9% of varroa mite

mortality for varroa control under Egyptian conditions. Data in Tables (1 and 2) showed that the highest number of varroa falling on the sheet was recorded after the first treatment and clearly decreased until the end of treatments.

Table (1): The reduction percentages of infection on adult in honey bee colonies treated with essential oils and formic acid in January 2021.

Date	Treatment	Control		Before treatment Adult	Concentrations No of fallen of varroa			After treatment Adult	Reduction % Adult
		Before	After		%25	%50	%75		
January									
First treatment	Camphor oil	32	28	28	22a	28b	30c	7	71.4
Second		30	27	26	25b	26b	27b	5	78.6
Third		27	25	20	20a	20a	10a	3	83.8
Fourth		23	20	18	7a	5a	3a	2	87.2
First	Mint oil	32	28	30	23a	25b	28b	10	61.9
Second		30	27	28	20a	23a	25a	8	68.3
Third		27	25	26	15a	18a	16a	6	75.1
Fourth		23	20	21	13a	12a	11a	5	72.6
First	Anise oil	32	28	27	20a	21a	22a	12	49.2
Second		30	27	25	18a	20a	20a	10	55.6
Third		27	25	23	17a	18a	19a	8	62.4
Fourth		23	20	21	15a	14a	12a	7	61.7
First	Formic acid	32	28	24	30c	30c	30c	6	71.5
Second		30	27	22	28b	28b	28b	4	79.8
Third		27	25	20	15a	15a	15a	3	83.8
Fourth		23	20	20	2a	2a	2a	2	88.5

Table (2): The reduction percentages of infection on adult in honey bee colonies treated with essential oils and formic acid in September 2021.

Date	Treatment	Control		Before treatment Adult	Concentrations No of fallen of varroa			After treatment Adult	Reduction % Adult
		Before	After		%25	%50	%75		
September									
First treatment	Camphor oil	30	26	26	25b	27b	29c	6	73.4
Second		28	25	24	23a	26b	27b	4	81.4
Third		27	24	22	20a	24a	15a	3	84.7
Fourth		22	20	21	8a	6a	2a	2	89.6
First	Mint oil	30	26	28	24a	26b	28b	12	50.6
Second		28	25	24	22a	24a	26b	10	53.4
Third		27	24	22	17a	18a	14a	8	59.1
Fourth		22	20	19	14a	13a	10a	6	65.3
First	Anise oil	30	26	26	20a	23a	25b	13	42.4
Second		28	25	23	18a	20a	22a	11	46.5
Third		27	24	22	17a	19a	20a	10	48.9
Fourth		22	20	20	16a	14a	13a	8	56
First	Formic acid	30	26	27	29c	29c	29c	7	70.1
Second		28	25	25	28b	28b	28b	5	77.6
Third		27	24	23	12a	12a	12a	3	85.4
Fourth		22	20	24	2a	2a	2a	2	94.5

Data in Tables (3 and 4) showed that the reduction percentages of infection on brood in colonies treated

with formic acid and essential oils in January recorded (86.3% formic acid), (81.5% camphor oil) , (65.7% mint oil)

,(56.7% anise oil) and recorded in September the reduction of infection of formic acid , camphor oil , mint oil and anise oil (86.9%), (82.1%) , (63.5 %) ,(56.2%) after treatment, respectively. Results showed that camphor oil is effective against *V. destructor* and safe

for bees. Several authors have evaluated essential oils as control agents for varroa (Imdorf *et al.*, 1999; Ariana *et al.*,2002 and Ismail *et al.*, 2006). Data agreement with May-Itza *et al.* (2007). Statistical analysis showed that highly significance between treatments.

Table (3): The reduction percentages of infection on brood in honey bee colonies treated with essential oils and formic acid in January 2021.

Date	Treatment	Control		Before Treatment	After Treatment	Reduction %
January		Before	After	Brood	Brood	Brood
First treatment	Camphor oil	33	30	25	11	51.6
Second		31	27	23	10	50.1
Third		28	25	22	6	59.3
Fourth		26	21	20	3	81.5
First	Mint oil	33	30	23	12	42.7
Second		31	27	22	10	47.9
Third		28	25	20	7	60.8
Fourth		26	21	18	5	65.7
First	Anise oil	33	30	27	14	43
Second		31	27	25	12	44.9
Third		28	25	23	10	51.4
Fourth		26	21	20	7	56.7
First	Formic acid	33	30	26	9	62
Second		31	27	23	7	65.1
Third		28	25	22	5	74.6
Fourth		26	21	18	2	86.3

Table (4): The reduction percentages of infection on brood in honey bee colonies treated with essential oils and formic acid in September 2021.

Date	Treatment	Control		Before Treatment	After Treatment	Reduction %
September		Before	After	Brood	Brood	Brood
First treatment	Camphor oil	30	27	28	10	60.4
Second		29	25	25	8	62.9
Third		27	23	24	6	70.7
Fourth		25	19	22	3	82.1
First	Mint oil	30	27	25	11	51.2
Second		29	25	22	9	52.6
Third		27	23	20	8	53.1
Fourth		25	19	18	5	63.5
First	Anise oil	30	27	27	13	46.6
Second		29	25	24	11	46.8
Third		27	23	23	9	54.1
Fourth		25	19	21	7	56.2
First	Formic acid	30	27	24	8	63
Second		29	25	23	6	69.8
Third		27	23	22	4	78.7
Fourth		25	19	20	2	86.9

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Effectiveness of plant growth regulators and biocides against some stored grain insects

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Abstract

Use of synthetic insecticides poses a serious hazard to humans and wildlife because of their adverse effects on the environment. So, the present study aimed to investigate newer approaches for controlling certain economic stored product insects, that achieve the efficient insecticidal activity, meanwhile leading to no detrimental effects to humans and the environment this respect, the following approaches were investigated: Azadirachtin revealed remarkable efficient on the metamorphosis of *Trogoderma granarium* Everts (Coleoptera: Dermestidae). These effects were somewhat similar to those of the synthetic chitin synthesis inhibitor, hexaflumuron, and were dependent on concentration. Azadirachtin showed significant ovicidal action against *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Fabricius), (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) but the action was generally less powerful than that of the IGR, hexaflumuron. The biocide, *Bacillus thuringiensis* (B.T.) exerted a weak entomopathogenic effect against adults of *Rhyzopertha dominica* (Fabricius) (Coleoptera: Bostrichidae) at concentrations ≥ 500 mg/kg grains. The effect was also poorly exhibited against larvae of *T. granarium*. The considerable entomo-pathogenic effect of the fungal bioinsecticide, *Beauveria bassiana* against adults of *R. dominica* was obtained at the concentration, 25 ml/kg grains (750×10^6 conidia/kg grains) at 65% relative humidity, hence 100% reduction of progeny was achieved. However, the effect was poorly exerted against larvae of *T. granarium* (at 25 ml/kg grains and 65% R.H., 18% reduction of progeny was observed). In all cases, the effect was slightly improved by raising the humidity.

Introduction

Stored grain of almost any kind is subject to attack by insects, which are highly specialized and in most cases are of small size with high reproductive potential. Therefore, they are easily concealed in grain and have been carried to all parts of the world. Under storage conditions, Insect infestation

causes loss above 50 to 60% under extreme situations (Kumar *et al.*, 2017; Liu *et al.*, 2020 and Poonam Jasrotia *et al.*, 2022). World Health Organization (WHO) and United Nation Environment Programme (UNEP) reported that pesticides are responsible for poisoning three million people and cause death for 200,000 each year

(Yadav *et al.*, 2015). Once established in a commodity they are usually difficult to control (Koehler, 2003). The potential hazards for mammals from conventional insecticides, the ecological consequences, and the increase of insect resistance to these insecticides have led to a search for newer advantageous classes of insecticides. Neem insecticides are derived from the seeds of the Indian neem tree, *Azadirachta indica* (Meliaceae) (Stone, 1992 and Kwasi *et al.*, 2011). Subsequent experiments in Germany demonstrated that azadirachtin also disrupted insect moulting at very low doses and interfered with reproduction in adult insects. (Mordue and Blackwell, 1993). Neem acts in many ways as like an insect growth regulator, feeding deterrent, oviposition deterrent, sterilizer, and inhibitor of chitin synthesis (Mondal and Chakraborty, 2016).

A comparative evaluation for the efficacy of *Bacillus thuringiensis* and neem seed oil on *Phthorimaea operculella* Zeller (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) has been carried out in the field and store. These two preparations were almost equally effective on the potato tuber moth infestation. In the store, neem seed oil (500ppm) was highly protective and was as effective as sevin. A combination of both neem and B.t (Delfin) significantly protected the tubers. This suggests the possible use of either neem seed oil or B.t. in combating the insect pest in the field or during storage (Salama and Salem 2000). IGRs appear to be effective against target insects with relative safety to mammals and the environment. IGRs have been tested and evaluated against insect pests in agriculture, forestry, and public health (Mian *et al.*, 1990). According to the Pesticide Manual (2000), of the British Crop Protection Council, hexaflumuron

acts as a chitin synthesis inhibitor, whereas “Pyriproxyfen” is a juvenile hormone mimic.

Beauveria bassiana conidia were formulated as a dustable powder (DP), as oil suspensions (OS), and as a novel hydrogenated rapeseed oil pellet. These formulations were assessed against *Sitophilus zeamais* Motschulsky (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) to study their potential use in the control of stored grain pests (Hidalgo *et al.*, 1998). *B. bassiana* with fipronil produced the highest mortality against *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst) (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae), *Rhyzopertha dominica* (F.) (Coleoptera, Bostrichidae) and *Sitophilus granarius* (L.) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) (Wakil *et al.*, 2022). The occurrence of entomopathogenic fungi isolated from stored grain insect pests included the ascomycetes *B. bassiana*. The cadavers of *T. castaneum* were significantly infected with the fungi followed by, *Sitophilus oryzae* L. (Coleoptera: Curculionidae), *R. dominica*, *Cryptolestes ferrugineus* (Stephens) (Coleoptera: Cucujidae) and *Callosobruchus maculatus* (F.) (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) (Wakil *et al.*, 2014). The findings revealed that *B. bassiana* and IGRs, e.g. pyriproxyfen are effective for the control of grain pests and can be used in integrated pest management (Bilal *et al.*, 2017).

The present study was planned to evaluate the insecticidal potency of the above-mentioned approaches (Neem insecticides, IGRs, *B. thuringiensis* and *B. bassiana*) against certain economically stored grain insects.

Materials and methods

1. Pesticides used:

1.1. Azadirachtin (Neemix 4.5% EC): Thermo Trilogy, Grace Drive, Columbia.

1.2. Hexaflumuron (Cousult 10% EC): Dow Agro Sciences.

1.3. Pyriproxyfen (Admiral 10% EC): Sumitomo chemical Company.

1.4. The bioinsecticide:

1.4.1. *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Xentari 13.3% W.G.): Abbott Laboratories. Chemical and Agricultural Products Division, North Chicago, 1L 60064, USA, provided by Bayer Company.

1.4.2. *Beauveria bassiana* (Biofly, a commercial liquid preparation containing 3×10^7 conidia/ml): El-Nasr Company for Fertilizers and Pesticides, Egypt.

2. Insects tested:

The original strains of all tested insects were obtained from the Department of Stored Product Pests, Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Egypt.

2.1. Cowpea weevil *Callosobruchus maculatus*:

Insects were maintained in small glass jars containing 150-200 unsexed adults and approximately 200 gm of cowpea seeds each. Jars were covered with muslin and kept in position with rubber bands. The cowpea seeds used for insect culture and the experiments were previously sterilized by freezing at -18°C for one week to kill any prior insect infestation, then stored in sealed polyethylene bags at 5°C until required for experiments. Newly emerged adults (0-24 hrs old) were used in the experiments. To obtain the adults, the culture medium was sieved to remove the old beetles therein and the emerging insects were collected for experiments.

2.2. Khapra beetle *Trogoderma granarium*:

Females lay eggs (30-60 eggs, each) inside grains or between them. Proper conditions for growth: 35°C ; 70% RH. The larval period ranges from 16-19 days, whereas the life span

duration ranges from 24-27 days. Insects were maintained in the laboratory at 70 ± 5 RH., in small jars each containing 200-400 adults and 400 gm of crushed wheat grain. Jars were covered with muslin cloth and fixed with rubber bands to be tightly closed. Newly emerged adults (0-24 hrs old) were used in the experiments.

2.3. Lesser grain borer *Rhizopertha dominica*:

The female lays 300-500 eggs singly or in clusters in the loose grain. They hatch in a few days. The larvae molt 2-4 times. They may feed on the flour produced by the boring of the adults or may bore directly into kernels that have been slightly damaged. They complete their growth within the grain, transform into white pupae and the adults cut their way out. The life cycle takes only a month or two, depending on the temperature. Both adults and larvae feed within the interiors of nearly all grains including rice and the kernels are reduced to mere shells. About 300 adults (1-3 days old) were added to 150 gm wheat kernels + 10 gm wheat flour in a small jar and covered with muslin. Jars were maintained under conditions of $34 \pm 3^\circ\text{C}$ and 70 ± 1 RH.

3. Preparation of grains and determination of their moisture content:

Wheat grains, *Triticum aestivum* var., Sakha 61 and cowpea seeds, *Vigna unguiculate* (L.), var., Azmerly, were used as a medium, carrying the tested insects. Grains were sterilized by freezing at -18°C for 1 week to kill off any prior infestation. The moisture contents of these grains were measured by oven-drying duplicate samples each of 5 gm, at 130°C for 1 hour, then calculated from the following formula:

$$\% \text{ Moisture content} = \frac{(\text{Initial grain wt} - \text{Final grain wt})}{\text{Initial grain wt}} \times 100$$

The grains were stored in sealed polyethylene bags in a refrigerator at 5°C as required for experiments.

4. Growth regulating effect:

The effect of azadirachtin on the metamorphosis of the khapra beetle *T. granarium*, in comparison to that of the conventional IGRs, hexaflumuron and pyriproxyfen was evaluated. Wheat grains were sterilized by heating in an oven at 60°C for 24 hrs. Sterile grains were treated with the tested toxicants as described before. 100 larvae (2nd instar) were transferred to a petri-dish (9 cm in diameter) containing 10 gm of treated grains. Another petri-dish containing 10 gm of non-treated grains carrying the same number of insects, served as control. Three replicates were made for each treatment. Dishes were kept under complete darkness and laboratory conditions for 30 days. Throughout and after this period the following parameters were recorded: % of abnormal larvae, larval period, % of pupation, % of abnormal pupae, pupal period, % of adult emergency, and % reduction of F1 progeny, calculated as follows:

$$\% \text{ Reduction in progeny} = [(C-T)/C] \times 100$$

(El-Zun, 1998).

Where:

C = No. of adults emerged in control.

T = No. of adults emerged in treatment.

5. Ovicidal action:

The ovicidal action of azadirachtin, hexaflumuron, and pyriproxyfen was evaluated against cowpea weevil, *C. maculatus*. The effect on metamorphosis when exposing eggs to these toxicants was studied as well. Serial concentrations of the pesticides were prepared in water. 20 gm of cowpea seeds carrying 230-250 eggs were immersed in the dilution of each concentration for one minute. Seeds carrying the eggs were left to dry, transferred to a petri-dish, and stored under complete darkness and laboratory conditions for 4-5 days. Three replicates were made for each

concentration. After this period, egg-hatching was examined and % of hatchability was calculated. Survival of emerged larvae were allowed to complete their life cycle. Hence, the following parameters were determined: Larval/pupal period, adult emergency (%), and reduction of progeny (%). It is known that larvae and pupae of cowpea weevil infest seeds internally, therefore, the total period of larval and pupal stages could be examined.

6. The entomopathogenic effect of the tested microbials:

The entomopathogenic of B.T. and the fungus, *B. bassiana* against adults of the lesser grain borer, *R. dominica*, and larvae of *T. granarium* was evaluated. The biocides were diluted in water and mixed thoroughly with sterile wheat grains (8.5% moisture content) to form serial concentrations as described before. 50 adults of *R. dominica* or 100 larvae (2nd instar) of *T. granarium* were confined to 10 gm of treated grains (For each concentration) in a 9 cm-petri dish and this was replicated four times. In control trials, grains were mixed only with water. Dishes were kept under complete darkness at 30° ± 2°C and 70 ± 5 RH. for 21 days (BT. treatments) or 11 days (Fungal treatments). During these durations, mortality counts were periodically recorded. At the end of each period, survival and dead parent adults were removed and offspring were allowed to complete their life cycle. Ultimately, No. of emerged adults was recorded and the percent, of reduction in F₁ adult progeny, was calculated as described before. The entomopathogenic effect of the fungal preparation, *B. bassiana* was carried out at three levels of ambient relative humidity (RH.) i.e., 65, 85, and 100%. Dishes containing insects confined to treated grains were kept for 11 days in tightly-closed glass jars (50 × 30 × 25 cm). Relative humidity was adjusted inside the jars by the method of Solomon (1951) with some modifications. Concentrations of pure KOH were prepared in distilled water,

i.e., 27.3, 15.8, and 0.0%, to attain 65, 85 and 100 % RH., respectively. 100 ml of each concentration was transferred to a 100 ml glass beaker. One beaker was placed inside each jar and this represented one replicate of biocidal treatments. The attained R.H was checked by a hygrometer placed inside the closed jar. Throughout the test period, the temperature ranged from 26-30°C.

7. Statistical analysis:

The results were analyzed by one-way analysis of variance ANOVA followed by the Least Significant Difference (LSD test). P values of ≤ 0.05 were considered significant. The lethal concentration for 50% mortality LC₅₀ was determined by log probit analysis. Data were analyzed by chi-square values.

The analysis of data was calculated with SPSS program version 24.0 windows (SPSS Inc., IBM Corp.).

Results and discussion

1. Growth regulating effect of Azadirachtin on *T. granarium*:

The effect of azadirachtin on the development and metamorphosis of khapra beetle, *T. granarium* was investigated. Larvae (2nd instar) were confined to treated grain for 30 days. Hexaflumuron (A chitin synthesis inhibitor) and pyriproxyfen (A juvenile hormone mimic) were evaluated for comparison as standard insect growth regulators (IGR). LC₅₀ of azadirachtin against adults of *C. maculatus*, and *T. granarium* after 24 hrs. exposure was found to be > 1500 mg a.i/kg grains (Table 1).

Table (1): Toxicity of Azadirachtin against adults of cowpea weevil *Callosobruchus maculatus* and khapra beetle *Trogoderma granarium* after 24 hrs. exposure to treated grains.

Toxicant	LC ₅₀ (mg/kg grains)	
	<i>Callosobruchus maculatus</i>	<i>Trogoderma granarium</i>
Azadirachtin	> 1500	> 1500

Results are recorded in Tables (2-4). Data presented in Table (2) show that azadirachtin at concentrations 0.25 mg/kg grain caused significant disruption in normal life processes of *T. granarium* and appeared as lethal morphogenetic effects, abnormalities and arrested development, ultimately resulting in suppression of F1 progeny. The morphogenetic activities of azadirachtin were less powerful than those of the standard IGRs particularly pyriproxyfen

whose activity was remarkably observed. In all cases, the effects were dose dependent. At 0.5 mg/kg grain, reductions of progeny were 46, 43 and 100% for azadirachtin, Hexaflumuron and pyriproxyfen, respectively. At 4 mg/kg grain (i.e the highest tested concentration), these percentages were 75, 82 and 100% for Azadirachtin, Hexaflumuron and pyriproxyfen, respectively.

Table (2): Effect of Azadirachtin mixed with wheat grains at various concentrations on the metamorphosis of khapra beetle* *Trogoderma granarium*.

Concentration (Mg/kg grains)	3 rd instar larvae*		Pupal stage			Progeny	
	Abnormal larvae (%)	Larval period (Days) Mean±SD	Pupation (%)	Abnormal pupae (%)	Pupal period (Days) Mean±SD	Adult emergency (%)	Reduction (%)
0.25	0.0 d	19 ±2b	90 a	17 c	3.5 ± 0.58 b	66 b	23.0 e
0.50	0.0 d	19 ±1b	90 a	27 b	3.5 ± 0.58 b	46 c	46.0 d
1.00	3.0 c	19 ±1b	89 a	30 b	5.5 ± 0.58 a	42 d	52.0 c
2.00	7.0 b	22 ±1a	87 b	53 a	5.0 ± 0.58 a	31 e	65.0 b
4.00	11.0 a	22 ±1a	73 c	55 a	5.5 ± 0.58 a	26 f	75.0 a
Control	0.0 d	19 ±2b	90 a	0.0 d	3.0 ± 1.00 b	86 a	0.0 f

In the same column, values followed by a common letter are not significantly different.

* A number of 400 larvae (2nd instar) were initially exposed to treated grains, the exposure on the same treated grain continued up to adult emergence.

Table (3): Effect of hexaflumuron mixed with wheat grains at various concentrations on the metamorphosis of khapra beetle* *Trogoderma granarium*.

Concentration (Mg/kg grains)	3 rd instar larvae*		Pupal stage			Progeny	
	Abnormal larvae (%)	Larval period (Days) Mean ± SD	Pupation (%)	Abnormal pupae (%)	Pupal period (Days) Mean ± SD	Adult emergency (%)	Reduction (%)
0.25	0.0 d	20.0 ± 2a	89 a	21 e	4 ± 1 bc	74 b	14 e
0.50	2.0 d	20.0 ± 2a	85 b	32 d	4 ± 1 bc	52 c	43 d
1.00	10.0 c	20.5±0.58a	80 c	40 c	5 ± 1 ab	43 d	55 c
2.00	13.0 b	21.0 ± 1a	77 d	55 b	6.5 ± 0.58 a	29 e	71 b
4.00	20.0 a	22.0 ± 2a	56 e	63 a	6.5 ± 0.58 a	25 f	82 a
Control	0.0 d	19.5±0.58a	90 a	0.0 f	3.0 ± 1.0 c	86 a	0.0 f

In the same column, values followed by a common letter are not significantly different.

* A number of 400 larvae (2nd instar) were initially exposed to treated grains, the exposure on the same treated grain continued up to adult emergence.

Table (4): Effect of Pyriproxyfen mixed with wheat grains at various concentrations on the metamorphosis of khapra beetle* *Trogoderma granarium*.

Concentration (Mg/kg grains)	3 rd instar larvae*		Pupal stage			Progeny	
	Abnormal larvae (%)	Larval period (Days) Mean ± SD	Pupation (%)	Abnormal pupae (%)	Pupal period (Days) Mean ± SD	Adult emergency (%)	Reduction (%)
0.25	0 a	24.5 ± 2.5d	90 a	52b	9.5 ± 0.58a	24 a	71 b
0.50	0 a	30.0 ± 2.5c	88 a	100a	-	0 c	100a
1.00	0 a	32.5 ± 2b	79 b	100a	-	0 c	100a
2.00	0 a	32.5 ± 2b	51 c	100a	-	0 c	100a
4.00	0 a	40.0 ± 2a	5 d	100a	-	0 c	100a
Control	0 a	19.5±0.58e	90 a	0.0c	3 ± 1b	86 b	0 c

In the same column, values followed by a common letter are not significantly different.

*A number of 400 larvae (2nd instar) were initially exposed to treated grains, the exposure on the same treated grain continued up to adult emergence

Figure (1): Abnormalities of 3rd instar larvae of *Trogoderma granarium* due to exposure to the toxicant at concentration, 4 mg/kg grain.

(A): Normal; (B): Azadirachtin; (C): Pyriproxyfen and (D): Hexaflumuron.

Figure (2): Abnormalities of pupae of *Trogoderma granarium* due to exposure to the toxicant at concentration, 1 mg/kg grain.

(A): Normal; (B): Azadirachtin; (C): Pyriproxyfen and (D): Hexaflumuron.

Malformations were observed especially for the pupal stage [% of deformed larvae and pupae of *T. granarium* were (11, 55); (20, 63); (0, %100) for azadirachtin, hexaflumuron and pyriproxyfen, respectively at the concentration 4 mg/kg grain]. The lower percentages of deformed larvae compared with those of pupae was certainly due to the short exposure period to the toxicants. Larvae of 2nd instar were exposed to treated grains and examination of deformed larvae was conducted on the 3rd instar larvae. Malformed larvae of azadirachtin or hexaflumuron treatments were smaller in size, conspicuously darker and setae became more brittle.

Larvae of pyriproxyfen appeared to be somewhat normal (Figure 1) and failed to pupate. Pupae of azadirachtin and other IGRs treatments were smaller in size, damaged and occasionally appeared as adultoids completely enclosed in intact pupal exuviae (Figure 2). Pupa-adult intermediates seemed to suffer a complete inhibition of ecdysis and severe deficiencies in the process of a new cuticle deposition.

In azadirachtin or hexaflumuron treatments, most larvae succeeded to reach the pupal stage depending on the concentration tested (% pupation was 73 and 56 for azadirachtin and hexaflumuron, respectively, at the concentration, 4 mg/kg grain). Data showed also that periods of larval stages were slightly affected due to azadirachtin or hexaflumuron treatments. In contrast, these periods were remarkably prolonged for pyriproxyfen treatment and the effect was dose-dependent (At 4 mg/kg grain, larval period., for pyriproxyfen was 40 days, versus 19.5 days for control larvae).

2. Ovicidal action and growth regulation effect against *Callosobruchus maculatus*:

The ovicidal action and the effect on metamorphosis of cowpea weevil, *C. maculatus* when exposing the eggs to aqueous concentrations of azadirachtin, hexaflumuron and pyriproxyfen were evaluated. Cowpea seeds carrying eggs were immersed in the dilutions of toxicants for one minute. After 4-5 days egg-hatching was examined. survivals of hatched (Confined to treated seeds were allowed

to complete their life cycle). Observations were made on larval + pupal periods, adult emergency and reduction of F₁ progeny. Results are

shown in Table (5). It was clear that azadirachtin and the two synthetic IGRs exerted significant ovidical action. The effect was dose-dependent.

Table (5): Ovicidal action and the effect on the metamorphosis of cowpea weevil *Callosobruchus maculatus* when exposing eggs* to aqueous concentrations of the tested pesticides.

Pesticides	Concentrations (ppm)											
	1250				2500				5000			
	Hatchability (%)	Larval + pupal period (days)	Adult emergency (%)	Reduction of progeny (%)	Hatchability (%)	Larval + pupal period (days)	Adult emergency (%)	Reduction of progeny (%)	Hatchability (%)	Larval + pupal period (days)	Adult emergency (%)	Reduction of progeny (%)
Azadirachtin	69 b	22 ± 2a	47 b	37 b	64 b	22 ± 2a	34 c	59 c	26 b	22 ± 2.5a	29 c	86 b
Hexaflumuron	55 c	22 ± 4a	73 a	27 c	34 d	22 ± 4a	51 d	68 b	9.0 c	22 ± 3.5a	40 b	94 a
Pyriproxyfen	60 c	24 ± 2a	18 c	80 a	44 c	24 ± 2a	13 d	89 a	26 b	25 ± 1.5a	13 d	94 a
Control	75 a	22 ± 3a	72 a	0.0 d	75 a	22 ± 3a	72 a	0.0 d	75 a	22 ± 2.5a	72 a	0.0 c

In the same column, values followed by a common letter are not significantly different.

* A number of 700 -750 eggs were initially treated for each concentration.

% Adult emergency = (No. of emerged adults/No. of hatched eggs) × 100

The highest effect was observed for hexaflumuron (At 5000 ppm, hatchability was 26, 9 and 26% for azadirachtin, hexaflumuron and pyriproxyfen, respectively). Durations of (larval + pupal) stages were not affected. As a general trend, the insecticidal activity of the tested compounds was not effective because both the larval and pupae phases were inside the cowpea seeds when roughly compared with those tested against *T. granarium*.

At a concentration of 5000 ppm, the larvae and pupae failed to reach the full adult stage, where the percentage of offspring exit was 29, 40 and 13% for azadirachtin, hexaflumuron and pyriproxyfen, respectively. Dead or deformed larvae or pupae could not be observed because they internally infested the seeds. Anyway, the most powerful compound in this respect was the JHA, pyriproxyfen followed by azadirachtin and hexaflumuron (At 5000 ppm, adult emergencies were 13,

29 and 40% corresponding to 94, 86 and 94% reduction of F₁ progeny, for pyriproxyfen, azadirachtin and hexaflumuron, respectively).

3. The entomopathogenic effects of the tested bioinsecticides:

The acute toxicity of the tested biocides was evaluated against adults of *C. maculatus* and *T. granarium*. LC₅₀ (24 hrs.) values and their fiducial limits were calculated. Results recorded in Table (6) show that B.T. and the fungal biocide are of very low acute toxic action (LC₅₀ of B.t.: >2000 mg/kg grain and for the fungus: 15.3 and 41 ml for *C. maculatus* and *T. granarium*, respectively). Therefore, the insecticidal properties of these agents could be achieved only through their pathogenic action that requires incubation periods for the spores to manifest their pathogenicity.

Table (6): Acute toxicity of the tested bioinsecticides against adults of *Callosobruchus maculatus* and *Trogoderma granarium* after 24 hrs. exposure to treated grains.

Insect	<i>B.t.</i> LC ₅₀ (mg/kg grain)	<i>Beauveria bassiana</i>	
		LC ₅₀ (ml */kg grain)	Confidence limits
<i>Callosobruchus maculatus</i>	> 2000	15.3	12.7 – 18.2
<i>Trogoderma granarium</i>	> 2000	41	39.0 – 42.3

*ml of the commercial liquid preparation, biofly

The entomopathogenic effect of *B.t.* and the fungus, *B. bassiana* against adults of the lesser grain borer, *R. dominica* and larvae of *T. granarium* was evaluated. Insects were confined to the treated grains for 21 days (*B.t.* treatments) or 11 days (Fungal

treatments) then cumulative mortalities were calculated. Reduction of F₁ adult progeny was examined as well. Result, for *B.t.* are recorded in Table (7). It was clear that *B.t.* preparation exerted weak insecticidal activity especially against larvae of *T. granarium*.

Table (7): Entomopathogenic effects of the biocide, *B.t.* against adults of the lesser grain borer *Rhyzopertha dominica* and 2nd instar larvae of *Trogoderma granarium*.

Concentration of <i>B.t.</i> (mg/kg grains)	<i>Rhyzopertha dominica</i> (Adults)		<i>Trogoderma granarium</i> (Larvae)	
	% Mortality ⁽¹⁾	% Reduction ⁽²⁾	% Mortality ⁽¹⁾	% Reduction ⁽²⁾
15	4.0 g	27 f	3 e	1 ef
30	16.0 f	41 e	4 e	3 ef
60	26.0 e	48 d	7 d	4 e
125	38.0 d	53 c	8 cd	13 d
250	58.0 c	71 b	10 c	22 c
500	78.0 b	75 b	12 bc	26 b
1000	96.0 a	82 a	24 a	45 a
Control	0.0 g	0.0 g	0.0 f	0.0 f

In the same column, values followed by a common letter are not significantly different.

⁽¹⁾ % of cumulative mortality following 21 days exposure to treated grains.

⁽²⁾ % reduction of progeny.

The considerable insecticidal activity against adults of *R. dominica* was achieved only at the highest tested concentration i.e., 1000 mg/kg as cumulative mortality was 96% and reduction of progeny was 82%. The activity was poorly exhibited against the larvae of *T. granarium* even at the highest concentration (Mortality and reduction of progeny were 24 and 45%, respectively).

The entomo-pathogenic effect of the

fungal bioinsecticide *B. bassiana* was poorly observed and was dose-dependent, especially against larvae of *T. granarium*. The considerable effect against adults of *R. dominica* was obtained at the concentration 25 ml/kg grain (750×10^6 conidia/kg grain) at 65% RH., hence 100% cumulative mortality and % reduction of progeny was achieved against adults, of *R. dominica* (Table 8).

Table (8): Entomopathogenic effect of the fungal bioinsecticide, *Beauveria bassiana* against adults of the lesser grain borer, *Rhyzopertha dominica* at various levels of humidity.

Concentration		Relative humidity					
		65%		85%		100%	
ml/kg Grains	Conidia/kg grains	% Mortality ⁽¹⁾	% Reduction ⁽²⁾	% Mortality ⁽¹⁾	% Reduction ⁽²⁾	% Mortality ⁽¹⁾	% Reduction ⁽²⁾
0.8	23.4×10^6	3.0 d	31 d	12 f	29 e	12 f	51 f
1.6	46.9×10^6	3.5 d	34 d	18 e	37 d	18 e	63 e
3	93.8×10^6	18 c	40 c	22 d	38 d	30 d	72 d
6	187.5×10^6	20 c	43 c	26 c	44 c	34 c	77 c
12.5	375×10^6	48 b	61 b	68 b	67 b	72 b	88 b
25	750×10^6	100 a					
Control	-	2.0 d	0.0 e	2 g	0.0 f	4.0 g	0.0 g

In the same column, values followed by a common letter are not significantly different.

⁽¹⁾ % of cumulative mortality following 11 days exposure to treated grains.

⁽²⁾ % reduction of adult progeny.

This concentration is thought to be high. If it is desired to treat a ton (1000 kg) of grain, thus twenty five litres of the commercial formulation will be required. Against *T. granarium* larvae the effect was much lower. (At 25 ml/kg and 65% R.H., 11% mortality and 18% reductions of progeny were observed (Table 9). In all cases, the effect was slightly improved by raising

the humidity. At 12.5 ml/kg grain reductions of progeny were 61 and 88% against *R. dominica* at relative humidities 65 and 100%, respectively. Against larvae of *T. granarium*, reduction of progeny increased from 13% to 33% when the humidity was raised from 65% to 100% at the same concentration.

Table (9): Entomopathogenic effect of the fungal bioinsecticide, *Beauveria bassiana* against 2nd instar larvae of *Trogoderma granarium* at various levels of humidity

Concentration		Relative humidity					
		65%		85%		100%	
ml/kg grains	Conidia/kg grains	% Mortality ⁽¹⁾	% Reduction ⁽²⁾	% Mortality ⁽¹⁾	% Reduction ⁽²⁾	% Mortality ⁽¹⁾	% Reduction ⁽²⁾
0.8	23.4 ×10 ⁶	0.0 e	2.0 e	0.0 e	5 e	0.0 e	3.0 g
1.6	46.9×10 ⁶	0.0 e	2.0 e	0.0 e	7 e	0.0 e	8.0 f
3	93.8×10 ⁶	0.0 e	3.0 d	0.0 e	8 d	0.0 e	13 e
6	187.5×10 ⁶	2.0 d	5.0 d	4.0 d	14 c	7.0 d	23 d
12.5	375×10 ⁶	5.0 c	13 c	11 c	16 c	19 c	33 c
25	750×10 ⁶	11 b	18 b	29 b	23 b	42 b	52 b
50	1500×10 ⁶	79 a	100 a	91 a	100 a	96 a	100 a
Control	-	0.0 e	0.0 f	0.0 e	0.0 f	0.0 e	0.0 h

In the same column, values followed by a common letter are not significantly different.

⁽¹⁾ % of cumulative mortality following 11 days exposure to treated grains.

⁽²⁾ % reduction of adult progeny.

Use of synthetic insecticides poses a serious hazard to human and wildlife because of their adverse effects on the environment. So, the present study aimed to investigate newer approaches for controlling certain economic stored product insects, that achieve the efficient insecticidal activity, meanwhile leading to no detrimental effects to humans and the environment this respect Our study included the effect of azadirachtin on the development and metamorphosis of khapra beetle, *T. granarium* was investigated. Larvae (2nd instar) were confined to treat grain for 30 days. Hexaflumuron (A chitin synthesis inhibitor) and pyriproxyfen (A juvenile hormone mimic) were evaluated for comparison as standard insect growth regulators (IGR). Azadirachtin showed considerable feeding deterrent effects against larvae of khapra beetle *T. granarium* at concentrations ≥ 125

mg/kg grains. The effect was concentration-dependent.

Azadirachtin revealed remarkable effects on the metamorphosis of *T. granarium* at concentrations ≥ 4 mg/kg grains. These effects were somewhat similar to those of the synthetic chitin synthesis inhibitor, hexaflumuron, and were dependent on concentration. The results are consistent with other findings on freshly treated grain, the application rate of 5 mg/kg of azadirachtin was effective in inhibiting F1 progeny production against *R. dominica* (Rahim, 1998). Salima *et al.* (2021) found that the toxicity of azadirachtin was increased by increasing concentration and exposure time against *S. granarius*. Our results revealed that pyriproxyfen treatment At 4 mg/kg grain, larval period., was 40 days, versus 19.5 days for control larvae.

Pyriproxyfen is an insect growth regulator with juvenile hormone (JH)

mimetic activity. Such JH analogues work by disrupting the development (Metamorphosis) of Juvenile insects. Late stage larval insects are most susceptible to the effects of JH analogues (Alejandro *et al.*, 2020). Browers (1971) reported that “the action of JHA sometimes prolongs larval development by delaying or preventing pupation. Lewis and Forschler (2017) found that chitin-synthesis inhibitors such as benzoylphenyl ureas were effective at killing all immature stages of a wide range of insect species including the internal grain feeders.

Our results revealed that azadirachtin at 1250-5000 ppm showed significant ovicidal action against *C. maculatus*, but the action was generally less powerful than that of the IGR, hexaflumuron (% Hatchability of azadirachtin at 5000 ppm was 26% versus 9 and 75% for hexaflumuron and control, respectively). Insect juvenile hormones and their analogues have been found to block embryonic development of treated eggs (Retnakaran, 1970) and thus, reduce oviposition. It was found that neem acted not only as an oviposition suppressant but also as an ovicide.

In laboratory experiments, Mankanjuola (1989) found that all extracts of neem leaf and seed significantly reduced oviposition, percent hatched eggs and percent adult emergence of *C. maculatus* on treated cowpeas. The ovicidal actions of neem oil were also observed by Ba-Angood and Al-Sunaidy (2003). Fenoxycarb and pyriproxyfen applied topically to Indian meal moth eggs for several seconds prevented completion of embryonic development, egg hatch or early larval development depending on the time and concentration of the application (Silhacek *et al.*, 1994).

The susceptibility of freshly laid eggs to direct treatment with IGRs or to

transovarial activity could lead to a treatment protocol that takes advantage of effects on embryogenesis (Oberlander *et al.* 1997). Also, our study revealed that the biocide, B.T. exerted weak entomopathogenic effects against adults of *R. dominica* at concentrations ≥ 500 mg/kg grains. The effect was also poorly exhibited against larvae of *T. granarium* (Mortality of *R. dominica* adults following 21 days of exposure to a concentration of 500 mg/kg grains was 78% versus 12% for larvae of *T. granarium*).

The considerable entomopathogenic effect of the fungal bioinsecticide, *B. bassiana* against adults of *R. dominica* was obtained at the concentration, 25 ml/kg grains (750×10^6 conidia/kg grains) at 65% relative humidity, hence 100% reduction of progeny was achieved. However, the effect was poorly exerted against larvae of *T. granarium* (At 25 ml/kg grains and 65% RH, 18% reduction of progeny was observed). In all cases, the effect was slightly improved by raising the humidity. Arthur and Brown (1994) evaluated B.t. formulations for insect control in stored peanuts after 8 months of treatment, *T. castaneum* populations in treated peanuts were not significantly different from the untreated controls. Beegle (1996) and Mikel *et al.* (2020) tested the efficacy of 36 isolates, representative of all available subspecies of B.t. against larvae and adults of *R. dominica*. They found that spore-crystal complexes of B.t. subsp. darmstadiensis isolates from Germany were effective against larvae. Isolates of the same subspecies from the USA and Japan were not effective. The degree of control achieved by even the best isolate was not economically satisfactory.

Kaelin *et al.* (1999) tested three B.t. strains against larvae of the cigarette beetle *Lasioderma serricornis* (F.) (Coleoptera: Anobiidae). The

responses to spore/crystal suspensions from all strains were in the range of 60-80% mortality after 7 days. The purified parasporal crystals showed a slightly lower insecticidal activity. Larvae surviving after exposure to sublethal levels of B.t. crystal proteins for 3-10 days could complete their life cycle on a normal diet without retardation. The researchers suggested that some adverse biological effects induced in *L. serricornis* by sublethal amounts of B.t. crystal proteins may be reversible and that larvae could recover from initial exposure.

In conclusion, Kaelin *et al.* (1999) concluded that neither B.t. strains isolated from stored tobacco more than two B.t. commercial products reached satisfactory levels of mortality and potency at the required times and doses. However, Mummigatti *et al.* (1994) and Sedlacek (1996) have reported on the susceptibility of stored grain coleopteran pests to B.t. subsp. tenebrions and other strains. B.t. is a Gram-positive sporulating bacterium that has been used as a biocontrol agent for more than 30 years. More than 30 different B.t. subspecies and insecticidal crystal proteins have been described which differ in insect host range, with over 90 genes cloned and sequenced (Cannon, 1996). B.t. preparations were exploited as biological control agents against susceptible species of insects of the orders, Lepidoptera, Diptera, Homoptera and very recently Coleoptera (El-Hamady, 1997).

The findings revealed that *Beauveria bassiana* and IGRs, e.g., pyriproxyfen are effective in the control of grain pests and can be used in integrated pest management (Bilal *et al.*, 2017). Wakil *et al.* (2014) reported that the cadavers of *T. castaneum* were significantly infected by *B. bassiana*. Searle and Doberski (1984) found that relative humidity and temperature

played a major role in the infection of adult *Oryzaephilus surinamensis* (L.) (Coleoptera: Silvanidae) by *B. bassiana*. At 100 % R.H., they recorded 100% mortality at day 20 after inoculation.

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Role of GC/MS analysis in early detection and poisonous compounds of infested cowpea seeds with *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Coleoptera: Bruchidae)

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Abstract

Insects cause a high loss in stored grains, *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Fabricius) (Coleoptera: Bruchidae). Mylabridae is one of the most important cowpea seed (*Vigna unguiculata*) pests and causes severe damage to the stored cowpea in several regions of the world. To decrease these losses and attained of safe storage for stored grain products, there is a need to use advanced insect infestation detection methods. Based on gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis of volatile chemical compounds (VCCs), the current work investigated the early detection of *C. maculatus* infestation in cowpea seeds and the impact of boiling (cooking) on hazardous chemicals compounds of infested cowpea seeds with *C. maculatus*. According to the findings of the GC-MS analysis, *C. maculatus* infestation caused extreme changes in the chemical constituents of cowpea seeds. Only infested cowpea seeds were ten VCCs found; boiling (Cooking) had no effect on them. Seven VCCs exposed in *C. maculatus* adults were also present in cowpea seeds affected by the same insect. These VCCs can be utilized as a marker for early *C. maculatus* infestation of cowpea seeds. Infested cooked cowpea seeds contained three hazardous and harmful chemical compounds: stigmaterol, β -sitosterol, and di-(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate. From this study, it can be inferred that the GC-MS methodology might be employed as a means of early infestation detection as well as the harmful compounds present in the infested stored grains.

Introduction

One of the most significant pests of cowpea seeds (*Vigna unguiculata*) is the cowpea weevil (Fabricius) (Coleoptera: Bruchidae). Mylabridae, which caused severe damage to stored cowpea in tropical and subtropical regions of the world (Bagheri, 1996). A few essays study the impact of boiling (Cooking process) on the volatile chemical compounds (VCCs) of infested cowpea. Insect

infestation has been shown by Evangelisti *et al.* (1994) to negatively impact the chemical composition of plant foods. The main chemical components undergo significant modifications as a result of cooking (Słupski, 2010). Some toxic or non-toxic chemical compounds are produced during the cooking process as reaction products (Shamaila *et al.*, 1992).

Early detection and control of insects in the stored grains become necessary for applying corrective actions. The grain industry is very interested in applying insect-detection technologies to diminish loss percentage and enhance the goodness of grain seeds and grain-products (Laopongsit and Srzednicki, 2010). The development of this method would aim to identify VCCs that signify insect infestation. The use of GC-MS to find insect infestation in grains has been applied in incredibly few researches. Some chromatographic techniques, including gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS), have been used to find insect volatile chemical compounds in grain products (Seitz and Ram, 2004). According to Niu *et al.* (2016), the volatile compound 2-ethyl-2,5-cyclohexadiene-1,4-dione is only present in flour infested with *T. castaneum* and it can be a helpful for the early detection of *T. castaneum* in flour. According to a recent study by Elhefny and Abdelfattah (2022), GC-MS analysis of volatile compounds can differentiate *C. maculatus*-infested cowpea seeds apart from raw or cooked cowpea seeds. Stigmasterol and beta-sitosterol, two volatile chemical compounds that can be utilized in the infestation identification of stored cowpea seeds with *C. maculatus*, were found in infected and infested cooked cowpea seeds.

Infestation of stored grains with insects is considered the most important of global problems. This infestation caused a high loss in the stored grains and changes the properties of the grains quantitatively and qualitatively, this resulting in a decline in the economic value of the grains. A stored grain infestation results in immediate damage, deterioration of grain quality, loss of feed value, and hygiene issues (Trematerra *et al.*, 2000). The interest in application of the modern insect-

detection technologies has been raised in order that minimize the loss of grains and improve the quality of grain products.

Therefore, the aim of this work is to use GC-MS technique analysis of VCCs for early detection of *C. maculatus* infestation and toxic compounds in cowpea seeds.

Materials and methods

1. Infestation of seeds and insect rearing:

Cultivated adults of the tested insect, *C. maculatus*, were raised on sored cowpea seeds, *V. unguiculata* (black-eye peas) Variety Name SAMPEA 18. The seeds were stored in glass jars (Each holding about 500 ml) in the quiescent stage in accordance with the techniques of Abdelfattah and Boraie, (2017) and Elhefny and Abdelfattah (2022). Ten unsex insects per 10 g of seeds caused the infestation. The insect was reared in the Agriculture Research Centre, Dokki, Giza, Egypt's, Department of Stored Products and Grains Pests Laboratory, part of the Plant Protection Research Institute. The infected seeds were split into two groups, one of which was boiled in boiling water without dipping, and the other of which was not. Moreover, two groups of non-infested control seeds were also gathered, both cooked and uncooked. Three times each group was repeated.

2. Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC/ MS) analysis:

GC/MS equipment (Fisons, Model GC8000 Series 8035 With MSD800 Mass Spectrometer Quadrupole) determined and identified the VCCs of the four treatments or samples raw (non-infested), *C. maculatus* insects (Unsexed adults), infested and cooked infested of cowpea seeds} in accordance with (Khattab *et al.*, 2020). Ten seeds were included in each treatment.

Results and discussion

Study of VCCs using GC-MS

The GC-MS chromatograms of raw cowpea seeds, adults of *C. maculatus*, infected cowpea seeds, and cooked cowpea seeds with *C. maculatus* are shown in Figures (1-4), respectively.

1. Volatile chemical compounds from raw cowpea seeds *Callosobruchus maculatus* adults and *Callosobruchus maculatus* infested cowpea seeds:

According to data in Table (1) and Figures (1, 2 and 3), five VCCs

Table (1): Volatile compounds from *C. maculatus* adults, raw cowpea, and *C. maculatus*-infested cowpea seeds were identified and determined by GC-MS.

No.	RT	Volatile compounds	Compound percentage (%)		
			<i>Callosobruchus maculatus</i>	Raw cowpea seeds	Infested cowpea seeds
1	6.07	2-Nitroacetophenone	ND	>1<5	ND
2	24.82	Sucrose	ND	>10<20	ND
3	38.22	Hexadecanoic acid, methyl ester	<1	>20<30	>10<20
4	39.14	Hexadecanoic acid	>10<20	ND	ND
5	42.00	9,12-Octadecadienoic acid 2-chloroethyl ester	ND	>30<40	ND
6	42.04	9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester	<1	ND	>10<20
7	42.18	8,11,14-Docosatrienoic, methyl ester	ND	>10<20	>5<10
8	42.62	9-Octadecanoic acid (Z)-methyl ester	>1<5	ND	>1<5
9	43.19	Z-11-Hexadecenoic acid	>30<40	ND	ND
10	54.06	Nonadecane	>1<5	ND	ND
11	55.35	Pentadecane	>5<10	ND	>5<10
12	57.48	Nonacosane	>1<5	ND	>5<10
13	58.02	Triacontane	>5<10	ND	>10<20
14	58.51	Tritriacontane	>5<10	ND	>10<20
15	60.41	Cholesterol	>5<10	ND	ND
16	62.63	Stigmasterol	ND	ND	>10<20
17	63.49	Beta-Sitosterol	ND	ND	>5<10

ND= not detected

RT= Retention time

Figure (1): GC-MS chromatogram of identified volatile compounds from the raw cowpea seeds.

were found in raw cowpea seeds, while 10 VCCs were found in infected cowpea seeds. Eleven VCCs were also found in mature *C. maculatus*. The VCCs in raw cowpea seeds changed as a result of the *C. maculatus* infestation. Only the infected cowpea seeds were found to have eight novel compounds; fresh cowpea seeds did not contain anyone.

Figure (2): GC-MS chromatogram of identified volatile compounds from *C. maculatus* adults.

Figure (3): GC-MS chromatogram of identified volatile compounds from infested cowpea seeds.

Figure (4): GC-MS chromatogram of identified volatile compounds from infested cooked cowpea seeds.

Both *C. maculatus* adults and *C. maculatus*-infested cowpea seeds contained seven VCCs: namely, Hexadecanoic acid, methyl ester; 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester; 9-Octadecanoic acid (Z)-, methyl ester, pentadecane, nonacosane, triacontane

and tritriacontane. Cowpea seeds with *C. maculatus* infestations had larger quantities of these compounds than did *C. maculatus* adults. Detection of these seven VCCs in the infested cowpea seeds may be a sign that *C. maculatus* has infected cowpea seeds.

The presence of these VCCs may be used as of an indicator an early infestation of cowpea seeds. One volatile chemical compound (VCC), known as cholesterol, was exclusively found in *C. maculatus* adults and was not found in cowpea seeds infected with *C. maculatus*. β -sitosterol (5–10%) and stigmasterol (10–20%) were two distinct VCCs found and identified in cowpea seeds infected with *C. maculatus* alone.

2. Effect of cooking on chemical compounds of infested cowpea seeds:

Ten compounds were detected in infested cooked cowpea seeds,

including seven novel compounds that were found in *C. maculatus* adults and the infested cowpea seeds, according to the results of the GC-MS analysis shown in Table (2) and Figures (2 and 3). This new compound especially two toxic compounds stigmasterol and beta-Sitosterol not affected by the cooking process quantitatively and qualitatively. On the other hand, during the cooking process, one VCC namely Di-(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (10-15%) was only found in infested cooked cowpea seeds; it was not found in infested cowpea.

Table (2): Volatile compounds from infested and infested cooked cowpea seeds with *C. maculatus* were identified and determined by GC-MS.

No.	RT	Volatile compounds	Compound percentage (%)	
			Infested cowpea	Infested cooked cowpea
1	38.22	Hexadecanoic acid, methyl ester	>10<15	>5<10
2	42.04	9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester	>10<15	>5<10
3	42.18	8,11,14-Docosatrienoic, methyl ester	>5<10	>5<10
4	42.62	9- Octadecanoic acid, methyl ester	>1<5	>1<5
5	51.21	Di-(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate	ND	>10<15
6	55.35	Pentadecane	>5<10	>5<10
7	57.48	Nonacosane	>5<10	>5<10
8	58.02	Triacontane	>10<15	>10<15
9	58.51	Tritriacontane	>10<15	>10<15
10	62.63	Stigmasterol	>10<15	>10<15
11	63.49	Beta-Sitosterol	>5<10	>10<15

ND= not detected

RT= Retention time

3. Effect of cooking on the toxic chemical compounds of infested cowpea seeds:

Beta-sitosterol and stigmasterol, two poisonous and significant VCCs, were found in cowpea seeds infected with *C. maculatus* but not detected in raw cowpea seeds. The act of cooking has no effect on these two VCCs. These two VCCs from the most significant phytosterols in both animals and plants. Stigmasterol and β -sitosterol are structurally related to cholesterol.

Also, a highly toxic compound called Di-(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate was

detected in the cooked cowpea seeds and infested with *C. maculatus*. This means that, this highly toxic compound is not affected by the cooking process.

Infestation of stored grains with insects is a universal problem and caused a high loss in the stored grains. In order to reduce loss and improve the quality of grain and grain-derived products, there has been an increase in interest in the application of contemporary insect detecting technologies. Based on GC-MS method analysis, the goal of this work is to use VCCs to detect insect infestation and

poisonous compounds in the stored grains.

Our results of the effect of infestation and cooking on the chemical composition of cowpea seeds infested with *C. maculatus* are very convenient with the results of Elhefny and Abdelfattah (2022) study who showed that, infestation and cooking caused a great change in cowpea seeds' volatile constituent. Some novel chemicals, such as stigmaterol and beta-sitosterol, which might be utilized as markers of *C. maculatus* infestations in cowpea seeds were found in infested cowpea seeds and cooked cowpea seeds infested with *C. maculatus* but not in the raw and cooked cowpea seeds. Additionally, they came to the conclusion that GC-MS can be differentiated between raw and *C. maculatus*-infested cowpea seeds. The findings of this assay were confirmed by Niu, *et al.* (2016) who found that distinct volatile chemical compounds from flour samples containing *T. castaneum* adults, healthy flour, and flour infected with *T. castaneum* were detected by GC-MS analysis. Just one volatile compound namely 2-ethyl-2,5-cyclohexadiene-1,4-dione, detected in the infested flour with *T. castaneum* and not detected with uninfected flour, this compound can be used as an indicator for the detection of *T. castaneum* in flour. De Quiros *et al.* (2000) conducted a study in which 27 chemical components were isolated from green beans and identified using GC-MS. The volatile component profile of green beans underwent significant modifications as a result of cooking. Additionally, Kermasha *et al.* (1988) investigated that all cooking methods resulted in a decrease in the amount of alcohol compounds and an increase in the amount of aldehydes and ketones in the French bean.

The inclusion of phytosterol esters in foods, which have the effect of

lowering cholesterol levels, has boosted interest in phytosterols (Stigmaterol and β -sitosterol) in recent years (Berger *et al.*, 2004). Studies in the field of toxicology have shown that stigmaterol and β -sitosterol have negative effects and lead to phytosterolemia (cardiovascular disease). Tao *et al.* (2019) demonstrated that the accumulation of stigmaterol, one of the phytosterol species, results in cardiac interstitial fibrosis, macrophage infiltration, and increased mortality without atherosclerosis. A stronger cardiac hazardous compound than β -sitosterol and campesterol, according to Tao *et al.* (2019), is stigmaterol. Significant mortality and stigmaterol accumulation are mostly correlated with cardiac damage. It is not well understood how stigmaterol results in heart fibrosis. In a different investigation, Malini and Vanithakumari (1990) demonstrated that β -sitosterol changed serum cholesterol levels in a way that had a tendency to have a hypocholesterolemic effect.

The two secondary metabolites of phytosterols, stigmaterol and β -sitosterol, are not toxic and pose no risk to human health, according to other toxicological investigations. In addition to being non-genotoxic, non-cytotoxic, and non-carcinogenic, stigmaterol and β -sitosterol had no long-term toxic consequences (Aguilar *et al.*, 2012 and Li *et al.*, 2012). Human liver cancer cells can be treated with β -sitosterol and stigmaterol, which can cause apoptosis (Li *et al.*, 2012). Both in vivo and in vitro, the stigmaterol had an inhibitory effect on hepatoma cells (Zhang *et al.*, 2008).

On the other hand, after cooking infested cowpea seeds, the highly toxic and extremely hazardous compound namely, Di-2-ethylhexyl phthalate (DEHP) was found in cowpea seeds. The findings of Lara *et al.* (2018),

which showed that phthalate esters (PAEs) are present in maize grain and flour, supported the existence of DEHP in cowpea seeds. In additional research, di-(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP) was found in soil and wheat grains, as demonstrated by Lü *et al.* (2018) and Shi *et al.* (2019). The PVC films and plastic containers used to cover and store food are made of phthalate esters (DEHP). Pollutants from the degradation of plastic films, such as phthalate esters (PAEs), could be constantly discharged into the soil and even accumulation in grains, endangering human health and food safety (Shi, *et al.*, 2019). In soils (Lü *et al.*, 2018 and Wang *et al.*, 2015), vegetables (Fu and Du, 2011 and Wang *et al.*, 2015), grains (Cai *et al.*, 2015), and cereals, (Schecter *et al.*, 2013 and Lu *et al.*, 2016), PAEs have been widely found. DEHP is heavily utilized in our daily life despite being extremely poisonous and dangerous to organism health. Exposure to DEHP has been demonstrated to have a number of negative consequences for both people and animals. DEHP has been found in several kinds of food and can enter the human body and hence causes its toxic hazards via several routes like ingestion; inhalation and also through intact skin (Ji *et al.*, 2014 and Liu *et al.*, 2017). The developmental toxicity of DEHP has also been investigated, and this includes impacts on brain development, intrauterine death, developmental delay, and morphological deformities and variants (Environmental Protection Agency, 2009). Results of GC-MS analysis of this work indicated that, the presence of seven volatile chemical compounds in the infested cowpea seeds can be used as an indicator to an early infestation of cowpea seeds with *C. maculatus*. Consequently, the volatile isolation technique (GC-MS) could be used as a monitor of *C. maculatus* in stored

grains. Two toxic compounds (β -sitosterol and stigmaterol) were only detected in the infested cowpea seeds samples and not affected by the cooking process, while infested cowpea seeds showed that the presence of highly toxic compound namely Di-2-ethylhexyl phthalate during the cooking process. Therefore, the cooking process of cowpea seed does not completely remove of the toxic compounds. These findings call the concern and attention for the pollution of grains crops in soil or plastic containers with some toxic compounds. According to this study must be aware of consuming infested or cooked infested cowpea seeds.

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Life cycle of *Caloglyphus betae* (Astigmata: Tyroglyphidae) fed on different kinds of food under laboratory conditions

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Abstract

Life cycle of *Caloglyphus betae* Attiah (Astigmata: Tyroglyphidae) was evaluated in the laboratory on animal feed, bean, sweet potato, mushroom, basterma and biscuit at $26 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, and $60 \pm 15\%$ R.H. relative humidity under laboratory conditions. Total development times from egg to adult stage were 7.24 ± 0.15 , 7.39 ± 0.28 , 7.05 ± 0.13 , 7.03 ± 0.16 , 6.98 ± 0.09 and 6.40 ± 0.19 days for female, while it was 6.11 ± 0.17 , 6.17 ± 0.18 , 6.10 ± 0.16 , 6.11 ± 0.17 , 6.05 ± 0.13 and 6.00 ± 0.17 days for male, at $26 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, and $60 \pm 15\%$ R.H. When feed on animal feed, bean, sweet potato, mushroom, basterma and biscuit, respectively. The pre-oviposition period was 2.00 ± 0.18 , 1.94 ± 0.28 , 1.62 ± 0.13 , 1.69 ± 0.16 , 1.69 ± 0.09 and 1.52 ± 0.22 days at $26 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, and $60 \pm 15\%$ R.H. when all the individual reread animal feed, bean, sweet potato, mushroom, basterma and biscuit, respectively. Generation time was average 9.24 ± 0.15 , 9.33 ± 0.00 , 8.67 ± 0.00 , 8.72 ± 0.13 , 8.67 ± 0.13 and 7.93 ± 0.27 at $26 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, and $60 \pm 15\%$ R.H., when all the individual reread animal feed, bean, sweet potato, mushroom, basterma and biscuit, respectively. Oviposition period was average 11.00 ± 3.18 , 10.00 ± 3.36 , 11.46 ± 3.07 , 10.69 ± 2.75 , 10.00 ± 2.04 and 9.79 ± 2.46 at $26 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, and $60 \pm 15\%$ R.H., when all the individual reread animal feed, bean, sweet potato, mushroom, basterma and biscuit, respectively. Post-Oviposition period was average 7.33 ± 4.64 , 7.67 ± 4.36 , 6.54 ± 5.56 , 5.62 ± 3.04 , 5.43 ± 3.30 , and 5.21 ± 4.41 at $26 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, and $60 \pm 15\%$ R.H., when all the individual reread animal feed, bean, sweet potato, mushroom, basterma and biscuit, respectively.

Introduction

The stored mites influence the weight and quality of stored product, the effect depends on their density and the length of infestation. If it was

evaluated separately the effect can be neglected, because the losses caused by mite contamination are quite higher and infested commodities are unsuitable for consumption due to contamination by

hazardous compounds. The mites change the quality of infested food by the production of secrets and feces. The massive infestation of mites changes the smell of stored products. The stored-product mites cause hypersensitivity not only for stored grain and farm workers, millers and bakers, but they also seriously endanger the health of the city population (Luczynska *et al.*, 1990 and Musken *et al.*, 2003).

The astigmatid mites are considered to be economically important pests, decreasing the quality of stored grain when present in large numbers. (Hage-Hamsten and Johansson, 1992; Tee, 1994 and Miller, 1995).

Stored mites flourish in warm and damp environments where they feed on protein rich substance such as grain, fungi and other micro-organisms. Mites infested food products undergo a series of changes in their chemical composition and flour prepared from contaminated grains is more acidic, fusty smell and bitter taste. Mites of sub-order Acaridida (Astigmata) are known to infest a wide variety of stored materials throughout the world.

These mites are a major cause of qualitative and quantitative losses to these stored materials, Nutrition is one on the important factors which has a modifying effect on growth and life span of mites, the growth of mite population is directly related with the biological as well as physical factors operating the ecosystem (Hughes, 1976 and Mostafa, 1994).

In this work, the authors studied the effects of various food type on duration and development of *Caloglyphus betae* Attiah (Astigmata: Tyroglyphidae).

Materials and methods

Mite species were collected from rice grains, wheat grains and animal feed. For obtaining pure culture

female and male adults were placed in the rearing plastic blocks (3× 3 ×0.5 cm) filled with a mixture of (Cement: Charcoal in ratio of 9: 1) as a substrate. The rearing plastic for each mite species contained yeast and a drop of water as a source of food and humidity, then the cell covered to prevent mite from escaping. Thirty blocks were used for each species. Each replicate contained a singly newly deposited egg which transferring by using of a fine camel brush. Thirty replicates were investigated twice daily under a stereomicroscope.

During each investigation add a drop of water in each block. The different biological aspects (Incubation period, hatching, moulting, mating, (Active and quiescent) larvae, protonymph, tritonymph, adult female and male were investigated, and recorded emergence males and females were sexed and then separated for testing the longevity and of females and males, respectively. A single female and male were placed together, to notice the mating behavior and calculated the life cycle, generation time, fecundity and life span, by counting the number of eggs laid every day.

1. Data recording:

Development from egg to adult was monitored three times a day in 8-hrs. intervals under a standard binocular microscope. When the mites reached adulthood, daily records of pre-oviposition, oviposition and post-oviposition periods and fecundity.

2. Data analysis:

One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and mean comparison using Fisher's least significant difference (LSD) were conducted for development time, the number of eggs deposited and number of preys consumed, using the Super ANOVA program (Gagnon *et al.*, 1989). Significance level was $P \leq 0.05$. The life table parameters of *C. betae*

were calculated with two sex software, developed by Chi (1988). The program calculates the intrinsic rate of increase (r_m), the finite rate of increase (λ), the net reproductive rate (R_o) and the mean generation time (T). The life table was constructed according to Birch (1948).

3. Statistical analysis:

Statistical analysis of obtained data was conducted using Proc ANOVA and GLM in SAS (SAS Institute, 1998). Mean separation were conducted using Duncan Multiple Range Test in the same program.

Results and discussion

Developmental time of different stages of *Caloglyphus betae* fed on six kinds of food under laboratory conditions:

Obtained results revealed that there are significant differences between male and female duration periods for all the food types, when the individual reared on animal feed, bean, sweet potato, mushroom, basterma and biscuit $26 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. with $60 \pm 15\%$ R.H.

1. Incubation period:

The eggs of *Caloglyphus betae* were hatched after 2.33 ± 0.00 , 2.36 ± 0.10 , 2.33 ± 0.00 , 2.33 ± 0.00 , 2.36 ± 0.09 and 2.33 ± 0.00 days at $26 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. with $60 \pm 15\%$ R.H., respectively for female, while they were 2.11 ± 0.17 , 2.11 ± 0.17 , 2.14 ± 0.18 , 2.11 ± 0.17 , 2.10 ± 0.16 and 2.07 ± 0.15 days at $26 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. with $60 \pm 15\%$ R.H., respectively for male on animal feed, bean, sweet potato, mushroom, basterma and biscuit. There were insignificant differences among the tested food types as shown in Table (1).

2. Larval stage:

The total larval periods were 2.47 ± 0.17 , 2.53 ± 0.17 , 2.44 ± 0.16 , 2.31 ± 0.09 , 2.29 ± 0.18 and 2.00 ± 0.13 days for female, while it was 2.00 ± 0.21 , 2.00 ± 0.21 , 1.95 ± 0.23 , 2.00 ± 0.21 , 1.95 ± 0.13 and 1.93 ± 0.15 days for male when feed on animal feed,

bean, sweet potato, mushroom, basterma and biscuit, respectively. The periods of larval stages were significantly differencing among mushroom, basterma and biscuit; being longest period was when feed on mushroom and shortest period was when feed on Biscuit.

3. Protonymphal stage:

The female protonymph Table (1) and Figure (1) lasted for 1.11 ± 0.16 , 1.14 ± 0.22 , 1.08 ± 0.15 , 1.10 ± 0.16 , 1.10 ± 0.16 and 1.00 ± 0.00 days when feed on animal feed, bean, sweet potato, mushroom, basterma and biscuit, respectively. at $26 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. with $60 \pm 15\%$ R.H. The male protonymph lasted 1.06 ± 0.14 , 1.00 ± 0.00 , 1.00 ± 0.00 , 1.06 ± 0.14 , 1.00 ± 0.00 and 1.00 ± 0.00 days at the same trend. The previous data showed that there were significant differences between the different tested diet at the protonymphal periods.

4. Tritonymphal stage:

The female Tritonymph Table (1) lasted for 1.33 ± 0.00 , 1.36 ± 0.10 , 1.21 ± 0.17 , 1.28 ± 0.18 , 1.24 ± 0.16 and 1.07 ± 0.14 days when feed on animal feed, bean, sweet potato, mushroom, basterma and biscuit, respectively. at $26 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. with $60 \pm 15\%$ R.H. The male Tritonymph lasted 0.94 ± 0.14 , 1.06 ± 0.14 , 1.00 ± 0.00 , 0.94 ± 0.14 , 1.00 ± 0.00 and 1.00 ± 0.00 days at the same trend. The previous data showed that there were significant differences between the different tested diet at the Tritonymphal periods.

5. Duration of total immatures:

The female immature which included (larval, protonymphal deutonymphal and Tritonymphal) stages lasted for 4.91 ± 0.15 , 5.03 ± 0.30 , 4.72 ± 0.13 , 4.69 ± 0.16 , 4.62 ± 0.12 and 4.07 ± 0.19 days, while those of male lasted 4.00 ± 0.00 , 4.06 ± 0.25 , 3.95 ± 0.23 , 4.00 ± 0.21 , 3.95 ± 0.13 and 3.93 ± 0.15 days at $26 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. with $60 \pm 15\%$ R.H. on animal feed, bean, sweet

potato, mushroom, basterma and biscuit, respectively. In general, the time required for female immature stage was longer than the male immature stage at different tested diet and the differences was significant as shown in Table (1).

6. Life cycle:

The period of life cycle (which included incubation, larval, protonymphal, deutonymphal and Tritonymphal stages) was completed in 7.24 ± 0.15 , 7.39 ± 0.28 , 7.05 ± 0.13 , 7.03 ± 0.16 , 6.98 ± 0.09 and 6.40 ± 0.19 days for female, while it was 6.11 ± 0.17 , 6.17 ± 0.18 , 6.10 ± 0.16 , 6.11 ± 0.17 , 6.05 ± 0.13 and 6.00 ± 0.17 days for male at $26 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. with $60 \pm 15\%$ R.H. on animal feed, bean, sweet potato, mushroom, basterma and biscuit, respectively (Table 1). In general, it can be concluded the Bean diet giving the longest life cycle and the differences between the rest tested diets was significant.

7. Longevity:

The longevity period Table (1). average 20.33 ± 7.23 , 19.61 ± 5.62 , 19.62 ± 6.45 , 18.00 ± 4.17 , 17.12 ± 3.63 and 16.52 ± 4.96 days for female while it was 17.00 ± 2.76 , 15.67 ± 6.89 , 17.43 ± 1.81 , 17.00 ± 2.97 , 14.86 ± 5.43 and 14.67 ± 5.89 days for male at $26 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. and $60 \pm 15\%$ R.H., on animal feed, bean, sweet potato, mushroom, basterma and biscuit, respectively. In general, it can be concluded the diet animal feed for females, and the diet Sweet Potato for males giving the longest longevity and the differences between the rest tested diets was significant.

8. Life span:

The life span Table (1). averaged (Included the period of life cycle and longevity) 27.58 ± 7.18 , 27.00 ± 5.57 , 26.67 ± 6.51 , 25.03 ± 4.16 , 24.10 ± 3.63 and 22.93 ± 5.04 days for female while it was 23.11 ± 2.71 ,

21.83 ± 6.81 , 23.52 ± 1.76 , 23.11 ± 2.86 , 20.90 ± 5.45 and 20.67 ± 5.96 days for male at $26 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$., and $60 \pm 15\%$ R.H., when all the individual reread animal feed, bean, sweet potato, mushroom, basterma and biscuit, respectively. In general, the time required for female life cycle, longevity and life span was longer than the male at different tested diets and the differences was significant as shown in Table (1).

9. Life table parameters

The preoviposition period Table (2). were on averaged 2.00 ± 0.18 , 1.94 ± 0.28 , 1.62 ± 0.13 , 1.69 ± 0.16 , 1.69 ± 0.09 and 1.52 ± 0.22 days respectively at $26 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. and $60 \pm 15\%$ R.H., when all the individual reread animal feed, bean, sweet potato, mushroom, basterma and biscuit, respectively. Generation time was average 9.24 ± 0.15 , 9.33 ± 0.00 , 8.67 ± 0.00 , 8.72 ± 0.13 , 8.67 ± 0.13 and 7.93 ± 0.27 at $26 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$., and $60 \pm 15\%$ R.H., when all the individual reread animal feed, bean, sweet potato, mushroom, basterma and biscuit, respectively.

Oviposition period was average 11.00 ± 3.18 , 10.00 ± 3.36 , 11.46 ± 3.07 , 10.69 ± 2.75 , 10.00 ± 2.04 and 9.79 ± 2.46 at $26 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$., and $60 \pm 15\%$ R.H., when all the individual reread animal feed, bean, sweet potato, mushroom, basterma and biscuit, respectively. Post-oviposition period was average 7.33 ± 4.64 , 7.67 ± 4.36 , 6.54 ± 5.56 , 5.62 ± 3.04 , 5.43 ± 3.30 , and 5.21 ± 4.41 at $26 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$., and $60 \pm 15\%$ R.H., when all the individual reread animal feed, bean, sweet potato, mushroom, basterma and biscuit, respectively. The previous data showed that there were significant differences between the effects of different tested temperature degrees as shown in Table (2).

The life table parameters of *Carpoglyphus lactis* were affected by different types of food (Taha *et al.*,

2019). Effect of food and temperature on developmental stages and fecundity of the grain mite, *Dermatophagoides farinae* Hughes (Acari: Acarididae: Pyroglyphidae) (Taha *et al.*, 2002).

Effect of different food types, on the biology, fecundity and life table parameters of the stored grain mite, *Gohieria fusca* (Oud.).

Table (1) : Developmental time of different stages of *Caloglyphus betae* fed on six kinds of food at $26 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, and $60 \pm 15\%$ R.H.

Food type	Duration time of adult female <i>Caloglyphus betae</i> (Days)			
	No.	Mean \pm SD	Max.	Min.
Pre-oviposition period				
Animal feed	(15)	2.00 \pm 0.18 _a	2.33	1.67
Bean	(14)	1.94 \pm 0.28 _a	2.33	1.67
Sweet Potato	(13)	1.62 \pm 0.13 _{bc}	1.67	1.33
Mushroom	(13)	1.69 \pm 0.16 _b	2.00	1.33
Basterma	(14)	1.69 \pm 0.09 _b	2.00	1.67
Biscuit	(14)	1.52 \pm 0.22 _c	2.00	1.33
Generation time				
Animal feed	(15)	9.24 \pm 0.15 _a	9.33	9.00
Bean	(14)	9.33 \pm 0.00 _a	9.33	9.33
Sweet Potato	(13)	8.67 \pm 0.00 _b	8.67	8.67
Mushroom	(13)	8.72 \pm 0.13 _b	9.00	8.67
Basterma	(14)	8.67 \pm 0.13 _b	9.00	8.33
Biscuit	(14)	7.93 \pm 0.27 _c	8.33	7.67
Oviposition period				
Animal feed	(15)	11.00 \pm 3.18 _a	14.00	2.00
Bean	(14)	10.00 \pm 3.36 _a	13.00	4.00
Sweet Potato	(13)	11.46 \pm 3.07 _a	14.00	4.00
Mushroom	(13)	10.69 \pm 2.75 _a	14.00	6.00
Basterma	(14)	10.00 \pm 2.04 _a	13.00	6.00
Biscuit	(14)	9.79 \pm 2.46 _a	13.00	4.00
Post-oviposition period				
Animal feed	(15)	7.33 \pm 4.64 _a	13.00	0.00
Bean	(14)	7.67 \pm 4.36 _a	12.00	0.00
Sweet Potato	(13)	6.54 \pm 5.56 _a	13.00	0.00
Mushroom	(13)	5.62 \pm 3.04 _a	10.00	0.00
Basterma	(14)	5.43 \pm 3.30 _a	13.00	1.00
Biscuit	(14)	5.21 \pm 4.41 _a	11.00	0.00

Means followed by a different subscript letter only within each period are significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$).

Table (2): Life table parameters of *Caloglyphus betae* feeding animal feed, bean, sweet potato, mushroom, basterma and biscuit.

Food type	Duration time of adult female <i>Caloglyphus betae</i> (days)			
	No.	Mean \pm SD	Max.	Min.
Pre-oviposition period				
Animal feed	(15)	2.00 \pm 0.18 _a	2.33	1.67
Bean	(14)	1.94 \pm 0.28 _a	2.33	1.67
Sweet Potato	(13)	1.62 \pm 0.13 _{bc}	1.67	1.33
Mushroom	(13)	1.69 \pm 0.16 _b	2.00	1.33
Basterma	(14)	1.69 \pm 0.09 _b	2.00	1.67
Biscuit	(14)	1.52 \pm 0.22 _c	2.00	1.33
Generation time				
Animal feed	(15)	9.24 \pm 0.15 _a	9.33	9.00
Bean	(14)	9.33 \pm 0.00 _a	9.33	9.33
Sweet Potato	(13)	8.67 \pm 0.00 _b	8.67	8.67
Mushroom	(13)	8.72 \pm 0.13 _b	9.00	8.67
Basterma	(14)	8.67 \pm 0.13 _b	9.00	8.33
Biscuit	(14)	7.93 \pm 0.27 _c	8.33	7.67
Oviposition period				
Animal feed	(15)	11.00 \pm 3.18 _a	14.00	2.00
Bean	(14)	10.00 \pm 3.36 _a	13.00	4.00
Sweet Potato	(13)	11.46 \pm 3.07 _a	14.00	4.00
Mushroom	(13)	10.69 \pm 2.75 _a	14.00	6.00
Basterma	(14)	10.00 \pm 2.04 _a	13.00	6.00
Biscuit	(14)	9.79 \pm 2.46 _a	13.00	4.00
Post-oviposition period				
Animal feed	(15)	7.33 \pm 4.64 _a	13.00	0.00
Bean	(14)	7.67 \pm 4.36 _a	12.00	0.00
Sweet Potato	(13)	6.54 \pm 5.56 _a	13.00	0.00
Mushroom	(13)	5.62 \pm 3.04 _a	10.00	0.00
Basterma	(14)	5.43 \pm 3.30 _a	13.00	1.00
Biscuit	(14)	5.21 \pm 4.41 _a	11.00	0.00

Means followed by a different subscript letter only within each period are significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$).

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Original articles are full length papers describing original research. The paper should not exceed 15 pages of double-spaced typed text (including abstract, tables, figures and references). One double-spaced typed page contains approximately 300-350 words. Reviews are normally by invitation from the Editor-in-Chief. However, authors are encouraged to submit a tentative title and a table of contents of a proposed review for consideration. These reviews should not exceed 20 pages of double-spaced typed text (Including abstract, tables, figures and references). Scientific notes and short communications to the Editor usually on matters of general concern to plant protection, are welcome but should not exceed 4 typed pages. The decision to publish submitted scientific notes and short communications with the Editor-in-Chief.

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Keywords: Most important words of paper. Should be from 4 to 6 words.

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Text formatting: Use a normal, plain font (e.g., 14 Point Times Roman) for text.

Abbreviations should be defined at first mention and used consistently thereafter. Authors should adhere to the rules governing scientific nomenclature to the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature. All biotica (crops, plants, insects, birds, mammals, etc.) should be identified by their scientific names including authors (and Order: Family) when the English term is first used in the main text, with the exception of common domestic plants and animals. Scientific names should be as follows: In the Title only give the Latin name but No authority or (Order: Family); in the Abstract all Latin names should be accompanied with the correct authority and with (Order: Family); in addition, at the first mention in the body of the text - and only then - these data should be given; authority, the order, family, should also go in the Key Words list.

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Cite references in the text by name and year in parentheses. Some examples:

- Negotiation research spans many disciplines (Abd-Rabou, 1996).
- This result was later contradicted (Simmons and Abd-Rabou, 2009).
- This effect has been widely studied (Abd-Rabou, 1998; Simmons *et al.*, 2002; Evans and Abd-Rabou, 2005 and Abd-Rabou *et al.*, 2005).

List style

Reference list entries should be alphabetized by the last names of the first author of each work.

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Abd-Rabou, S. (1998): The efficacy of indigenous parasitoids in the biological control of *Siphoninus phillyreae* (Homoptera: Aleyrodidae) on pomegranate in Egypt. Pan-Pacific Entomologists, 74 (3): 169-173.

Evans and Abd-Rabou (2005): Two new species and additional records of Egyptian Aphelinidae. Zootaxa, 833:1-7.

Simmons, A. and Abd-Rabou, S. (2006): Whitefly populations in vegetables crops with different fertilizers. 52nd Annual meeting of the South Carolina Entomological Society, Mc Cormick, Sc., October 19-20.

Abd-Rabou, S. and Simmons, A. M. (2012): *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) whitefly as a pest in Egypt. Advances In Agricultural Research In Egypt, 10 (1): 1-82.

Figures Line-drawing should be clear and of high quality. Cite all figures in numerical order in the manuscript.

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